

D4.3 - Report of the CRM-free, low environmental footprint Si production cells

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Document control sheet

Project	RESILEX – Resilient Enhancement for the Silicon Industry Leveraging the European matrix
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07
Grant Agreement Number	101058583
Coordinator	Iberian Sustainable Mining Cluster (ISMC)
Work package N°	4
Work package title	Sustainable, eco-design solar cells & modules
Work package leader	CSEM
Document title	D4.3-Report of the CRM-free, low environmental footprint Si production cells
Lead Beneficiary	CSEM
Dissemination level	Public
Authors	Laurie-Lou Senaud, Adeline Lanterne, Pia Vasquez
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Reviewer(s)	CEA (Adeline Lanterne for CSEM parts), CSEM (Laurie-Lou Senaud for CEA and LMGP parts) ISMC (Francisco J. Luque)
Issue date	May 2025

Version control table

Version	Date	Main changes
V1	14/04/2025	First contribution from Laurie-Lou Senaud, Adeline Lanterne, Pia Vasquez
V2	17/05/2025	New contribution from Laurie-Lou Senaud, Adeline Lanterne, Pia Vasquez
V3	25/05/2025	Review from Laurie-Lou Senaud
VFINAL	26/05/2025	Review from Adeline Lanterne
VFINAL2	28/05/2025	Review from ISMC (Francisco J. Luque)
VFINAL3	06/10/2025	Addition of Version control table and reviewers' names

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1. Executive summary

The deliverable D4.3 for the RESILEX project outlines the current status and future directions for the eco-design of passivated contact silicon solar cells, focusing on the reduction of indium, silver, and silicon consumption. Results of the approaches studied in RESILEX to reduce these strategic materials in heterojunction solar cells are presented in the report, starting with the reduction of one material and then moving to the simultaneous reduction of In + Ag or In + Si.

For the indium content reduction, three approaches were investigated:

- The reduction of the In-based TCO layer thickness, for In reduction above 70%
- The development of AZO layers as In-free TCOs by PVD
- The development of SnO₂ films as In-free TCOs using an atmospheric pressure, low-temperature, and low environmental footprint spatial atomic layer deposition technique (AP-SALD)

For the silver content reduction, two copper-based approaches were investigated:

- The use of copper-containing paste deposited by screen printing
- The use of a copper electroplating process

Only solar cell developments and performances are presented in the report. Module interconnection, lamination, and aging tests performed on these cells will be presented in Deliverable 4.4. During the project, the assessment of the environmental impact and the cost of the selected approaches were discussed with WP7 and guided our developments.

As a short conclusion:

- A successful combined reduction of indium by 72% and silver by 62% was demonstrated on large batches of SHJ solar cells on a pre-industrial pilot line, with no significant impact on performance. The work conducted to an increase the TRL of the approach up to TRL 7, and the results demonstrated compatibility with 25% cell efficiency on an industrial line.
- A second successful demonstration of the combination of indium reduction by 72% with copper plating metallization was obtained, again with no significant impact on SHJ performance, thus remaining compatible with 25% efficiency. The TRL of this approach was also increased with the demonstration of the compatibility and adaptability of the plating process with industrial precursors and industrial masking dielectrics.

- In addition, it was demonstrated that the same dielectric layers can be used both as copper-plating masks and as capping layers for thin TCOs, which are needed for the re-hydrogenation of the TCOs and for their anti-reflective properties. This led to the development of a very simple process for combining copper plating with In-less or In-free SHJ.
- State-of-the-art results were obtained for the development of In-free TCOs (AZO) with properties suitable for solar cell integration. Thanks to the optimization of the cell design, the developed AZO layer could be integrated on the rear side of IBC SHJ cells showing the potential of this structure for In-free SHJ. AZO was also successfully implemented on standard SHJ without performance losses when applied on front side only.
- The project also contributed to the development of a novel SALD setup for SnO_x thin film deposition with an industrially relevant deposition rate. SnO_x films are currently being tested in SHJ solar cells.

2. Introduction

One of the main objectives of WP4 of the RESILEX project is to reduce the environmental footprint of silicon heterojunction (SHJ) solar cells and to enhance their sustainability to move towards eco-designed photovoltaic solar cells. To achieve this goal part of WP4 aims to reduce the consumption of strategic raw materials in the solar cell: indium, silver, and silicon, and to investigate the use of crystalline silicon wafers made from revalorized silicon wastes. Specifically, this part of WP4 focuses on analysing the performance and on increasing the maturity (TRL) of the following approaches:

1. The development of In-less and In-free solar cells
2. The development of Ag-less and Ag-free solar cells
3. The use of thin silicon wafers
4. The use of revalorized silicon

The overall environmental footprint reduction and benefits of SHJ solar cells resulting from these developments (including processes, materials, and design) are investigated and analysed through process impact analysis conducted by the WP7 team.

Silicon heterojunction technology represents a highly promising pathway for next-generation industrial solar cell production, owing to a combination of performance and manufacturing advantages. Beyond its high-power conversion efficiency, SHJ benefits from a low-temperature fabrication process (below 230 °C) and a reduced number of process steps. It also exhibits a low temperature coefficient (typically below $-0.27 \text{ \%/}^\circ\text{C}$), ensuring excellent performance under real-world operating conditions. These characteristics result in a competitive environmental footprint, as detailed in deliverable D4.1.

In the context of the rapid expansion of the photovoltaic industry, SHJ solar cells represent an attractive solution, with manufacturing capacities already planned to exceed 218 GW/year in the near future. However, two major bottlenecks related to the supply of critical raw materials have been identified as limiting factors for this growth. Specifically, based on current material usage per cell, SHJ production would be constrained to approximately 171 GW/year if 20% of the global silver supply (as of 2019) were dedicated to the technology. The limitation is even more pronounced for indium, where the same allocation would restrict annual SHJ production to 95 GW [Zang2021].

In addition, only 32% of the silicon used in Europe is produced within the EU, making this element crucial for maintaining the competitiveness of European industry. On the

other hand, silicon wafers represent a significant environmental footprint of solar cell production due to the intense energy required for their purification and manufacturing processes. Therefore, reducing silicon consumption is a major lever for decreasing the environmental impact of silicon-based solar cells (see D4.1 for more details).

Leveraging economic and environmental sustainability in the silicon industry requires careful assessment of the entire supply chain from raw materials extraction up to final product fabrication. Factors impacting the environmental footprint can be linked to raw materials-related activities (extraction, synthetization, purification, etc.) as well as to processing steps (energy consumption, CO₂, greenhouse gas emissions, etc.). These considerations were introduced and discussed in deliverable D4.1 and are used to guide the development of this deliverable D4.3. A simplified schematics of the main factors that intervene in SHJ environmental footprint is shown in Figure 2-1. Solutions proposed in this deliverable address more specifically the "1(b) supply instability/scarcity of raw materials" factor by the development of In-free and Ag-free solar cells, and the "2(a) Energy intensive fabrication steps" factor by the study of alternative deposition technique. In addition, the 1(a) and 2(b) factors are considered when we studied the reduction of silicon consumption.

Figure 2-1 Schematics summarizing the main factors that intervene in the environmental footprint of SHJ solar cells.

Aligned with the RESILEX project's goals, the objective of this deliverable is to provide a detailed summary of the main results of the RESILEX project concerning CRM low, CRM-free and low environmental footprint silicon solar cells. Results regarding indium, silver and silicon reduction (bullet points 1-3) will be presented in this report, while the investigation of silicon revalorization (bullet point 4) will be addressed in Deliverable D4.5 at the end of the project.

3. CRM reduction in heterojunction solar cells

3.1. Silicon heterojunction solar cells

SHJ structure and process:

As introduced previously, the solar cell technology investigated in the RESILEX project is the silicon heterojunction (SHJ) technology. The fabrication steps of commercial SHJ solar cells are presented in the Figure 3-1 below and start with n-type monocrystalline silicon (c-Si(n)) wafers. First, the wafer is textured on both sides in an alkaline solution to create random pyramids and then wet chemically cleaned using different chemical baths. Then, the different material layers required for efficient light collection and extraction are deposited on both sides of the c-Si(n) wafer. The first deposited layers are thin blanket hydrogenated intrinsic amorphous silicon (a-Si:H(i)) films which are integrated on both sides of the wafer by plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) for surface passivation. Second, in the case of bifacial solar cells, the n-type and the p-type hydrogenated thin silicon layers are immediately deposited by PECVD on top of the a-Si:H(i) layers, at the front and back side respectively. These layers are in amorphous (a-Si:H(n/p)) or nanocrystalline (nc-Si:H(n/p)) phase and play the role of generated carriers (electrons and holes) selective layers. After the PECVD steps, transparent conductive oxide (TCO) layers are deposited using the magnetron sputtering techniques of physical vapour deposition (PVD) on both sides of the c-Si(n) wafer. The front TCO thickness is adapted to act as an efficient anti-reflecting-coating (ARC). The most commonly used and industrialised TCO is the indium tin oxide (ITO).

Figure 3-1: Schematics of the process steps to fabricate commercial bifacial SHJ solar cells investigated in the RESILEX project. The various materials layers required to build efficient solar cells are: (i) the n-type doped crystalline silicon bulk, (ii) the front and rear intrinsic and n- or p-type doped hydrogenated

amorphous silicon layers (a-Si:H(i/n/p)), (iii) the front and rear transparent conductive oxide (TCO), (iv) as well as the rear and front silver grid.

Finally, the metallic grids are applied by screen-printing a low-temperature silver paste at the front and back sides of the solar cells and completed with an annealing at around 200°C during few minutes. The process flows used to manufacture bifacial SHJ solar cells are depicted in Figure 3-1.

IBC SHJ:

In addition to the bifacial SHJ solar cell architecture, the WP4 of the RESILEX project investigates the interdigitated back contact (IBC) architecture as a promising alternative for indium-free SHJ solar cells. This architecture is characterized by the placement of all metallic grid electrodes on the rear side of the cell, which significantly mitigates shadowing losses at the front side. Furthermore, the IBC design incorporates indium-free transparent conductive oxides (TCO), enhancing its potential for sustainable and efficient solar energy conversion. This architecture exhibits distinct differences compared to SHJ bifacial cells, as illustrated in Figure 3-2 below, which presents a schematic description of the SHJ IBC process steps.

Figure 3-2 Schematics of the process steps to fabricate IBC SHJ solar cells investigated in the RESILEX project. The typical materials layers required to build efficient IBC solar cells are: (i) the rear n- and p-type doped hydrogenated nanocrystalline silicon layers (nc-Si:H(n/p)), (iii) the rear indium-free transparent conductive oxide (TCO), (iv) as well as the rear silver grid.

For the IBC architecture, the initial three process steps are similar to those of the bifacial SHJ cells. Following the deposition of a-Si:H(i) layers, an nc-Si:H(n) layer is applied to the rear side using a shadow mask to define the electron-collecting area. Subsequently, the mask is removed, and a full blanket nc-Si:H(p) layer is deposited, covering the entire back surface. On the front side, the thin a-Si:H(i) passivating film is overlaid with a silicon nitride (SiN_x) antireflective coating (ARC), which provides additional surface passivation, high transparency, and effective light coupling. After the PECVD steps, a full blanket indium-free TCO layer, specifically aluminium-zinc oxide (AZO), is deposited by PVD onto the nc-Si:H(p) layer at the back side. Finally, the metallic grids are applied by screen-printing a low-temperature silver paste onto the

back side of the c-Si(n) wafer, followed by annealing at approximately 200°C for a few minutes. As the final step for the IBC devices, the AZO layer sections between the silver grids are etched away using a light acidic solution.

3.2. State of the art of In reduction in SHJ technology

For SHJ cells, the transparent conductive oxide (TCO) layer must meet several key requirements to ensure high cell efficiency. These include low contact resistance with both the underlying active a-Si:H layers and the metal grid, low sheet resistance to enable efficient lateral charge transport, and high optical transmittance. In addition, the TCO must serve as an effective antireflective layer. To date, only indium-based materials successfully meet all these criteria, making indium tin oxide (ITO) the industry-standard TCO. In current industrial SHJ production, approximately 100 nm of ITO is deposited per side, measured as the equivalent thickness on a flat surface. Given the scarcity and price volatility of indium, reducing its consumption has become a strategic priority for the photovoltaic industry since 2020. Several approaches had already been explored prior to the start of this project and have continued to be actively investigated since then:

Figure 3-3 SHJ solar cells schemes with three Indium reduction approaches which are (i) the reduction of indium-based TCO thickness, (ii) the replacement of ITO with Indium-Free TCOs and (iii) the multilayer architectures.

1. Reduction of Indium-based TCO Thickness

The first approach consists simply in reducing the thickness of the ITO or, more generally, the indium-based TCO. When optimized on the rear side of the cell, this strategy can directly reduce indium consumption by up to 25% [Jay 2022]. However, when applied to the front side, reducing TCO thickness negatively impacts the optical properties of the stack, requiring the addition of an extra layer to maintain optimal anti-reflective performance. This layer can either be an indium-free TCO, as detailed in the

multilayer approach below, or a dielectric layer deposited by PECVD, forming a double anti-reflective coating (DARC).

Initial proof-of-concept results for this dielectric-based DARC configuration were obtained at CEA prior to the start of the project [Seron 2023]. Parallel studies have shown that a dielectric capping layer not only improves humidity resistance in cells with thin TCOs [Morales 2019] [Pirrot-Berson 2025], but also enhances TCO conductivity due to hydrogen doping effects [Herasimenka 2016].

Since 2022, there has been growing interest in this approach, with both simulations and SHJ prototypes featuring ITO thicknesses as low as 25 nm (equivalent on polished surfaces) being developed across various institutes [Han 2022] [Cruz 2022]. This trend illustrates the increasing maturity of the DARC process. However, industrial-scale reliability of this approach has yet to be demonstrated, particularly concerning its impact on module interconnection and long-term durability, which will need to be thoroughly evaluated.

2. Replacement of ITO with Indium-Free TCOs

This approach has the advantage to completely remove indium from the SHJ cells. Indium-free TCOs such as aluminum-doped zinc oxide (AZO) and tin dioxide (SnO_2) have been explored as sustainable alternatives. AZO, is particularly attractive due to its cost-effectiveness and shows promising results [Senaud 2022]. However, its poor stability under humidity, leading to degradation in cell performance, limits its direct use without additional protection [Cruz 2020] [Morales 2019]. Incorporating robust moisture barriers during encapsulation can address this, but may add complexity and cost. An alternative is to implement a DARC configuration using a dielectric layer similarly to thin TCOs.

Investigations of SnO_2 thin films deposited on SHJ solar cell structures show promising progress. Reactive plasma deposition of amorphous SnO_2 at low substrate temperatures as front transparent contact resulted in efficiency of 20.8%, only 0.3% lower than the ITO reference [Koida, T. 2023], [Sai, H. 2024]. The main challenge of replacing ITO by SnO_2 is the loss in lateral conductivity. Investigations in doping SnO_2 with several elements (F, Sb, Mg, Li, Cu among others) have resulted in improvements of the electrical properties of the intrinsic films [Dalapati, G. 2021] [Bakshi, S. 2025]. Indeed, fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) is currently a commercially available TCO, together with AZO and ITO and particularly advantageous for processes at temperatures up to 600°C. In this work, we investigate deposition of SnO_2 films using

atmospheric pressure, low temperature and low environmental footprint spatial atomic layer deposition (AP-SALD). Details on this deposition technique will be given in further sections.

3. Multilayer Architectures (In-Free + In-Rich TCO Combinations)

As discussed previously, due to the lower performance levels observed up to 2022 with fully indium-free TCOs in SHJ cells, the use of multilayer stacks combining indium-free and indium-based TCOs has been explored. Initial results demonstrated a performance enhancement when a thin interfacial indium-based TCO layer was introduced beneath the AZO layer [Dong 2023]. Other studies have reported improved long-term stability of AZO when capped with a thin ITO layer deposited on top [Schmid 2023]. Although this multilayer configuration still contains some indium, it enables a significant reduction in overall indium consumption while offering possibilities for good electrical and optical performance.

4. TCO-Free strategies

Finally, more radical approaches aim to eliminate TCO layers entirely. In that goal TCO-free architectures have been investigated at the proof-of-concept level, including the integration of graphene [Lancellotti 2020] or complete TCO removal [Li 2021] [He 2022]. However, their industrial viability remains unproven.

5. TCO deposition methods

Industrial-scale fabrication of TCOs for SHJ solar cells has been traditionally performed using PVD, particularly using the sputtering technique. The working principle of PVD technique lie on the erosion of a solid target by energetic ions in a plasma phase, further deposited on a substrate in a closed environment under vacuum [Sigmund 2023]. One major drawback of sputtering deposition of TCOs for solar cells is the damage induced by ion bombardment, resulting in loss of efficiency [Depeng 2022].

An alternative to sputtering for TCO deposition is atomic layer deposition (ALD), a promising technique for depositing thin films with high conformality, thickness and stoichiometry control. This high precision is due to the self-terminated reactions that take place at the sample surface, where gas-phase precursors react only at the chemically available reactions sites. Therefore, to deposit a film composed of elements A and B in an ALD reactor, precursor containing the element A will be injected during the time interval needed to fulfil all the available sites for A, as depicted in the

simplified schematics of Figure 3-4. Precursor containing the element B will be injected in the same way, after an intermediate purging step to remove excess precursor A and chemical byproducts from the ALD reactor. At the end of the purge step of precursor B, a monolayer of composition AB is formed.

Figure 3-4 Simplified schematics showing formation of a monolayer film composed by elements A and B using the ALD principle. This process is repeated the number of times needed to obtain the desired film thickness.

The problem of sputtering damage by ion bombardment is suppressed in ALD, given that reactions are thermally driven, being ALD a particular case of chemical vapor deposition (CVD). One major drawback of ALD is the long purging times needed after each species injection to remove precursor residuals and byproducts from the reactor, reducing the attractiveness for industrial applications. Atmospheric pressure spatial atomic layer deposition (AP-SALD) is an emerging tool for depositing thin films, applicable to a wide variety of industries [Poedt 2012]. The main advantage of AP-SALD with respect to traditional ALD is the high throughput derived from the spatially localized, continuous reactions induced by the physical displacement of the sample under a fixed reactor, instead of the sequential pulse-purge scheme proposed by ALD [Muñoz-Rojas 2019]. In this way, growth rates of films deposited with SALD can be up to two orders of magnitude faster than temporal ALD. Moreover, in the AP-SALD setup chemical reactions are confined to a narrow gap (< 100 μm) between the reactor and the sample surface, therefore film formation is driven by the partial pressures of gas columns projected from the reactor to the surface. In this way, a vacuum chamber is no longer needed, eliminating the costs associated to pumping systems. The localized nature of reactions near the surface also reduces chemical precursors consumption, in contrast to temporal ALD where the material is deposited all over the reactor enclosure [Weber 2023]. A simplified schematics showing the main differences between a traditional ALD and a spatial ALD setup is shown in the Figure 3-5.

For the development of In-free TCOs in the WP4, an AP-SALD setup of in-house manufacturing at LMGP is used to fabricate In-free TCO films to be tested in SHJ solar cell precursors fabricated at CEA.

Figure 3-5 Simplified schematics of an ALD (top) and SALD (bottom) reactors. In the ALD scheme, subsequent deposition-purge steps are separated by time intervals that need to be optimized to ensure physical separation of the reactants (metal and oxygen). In the SALD reactor, all precursors are injected continuously, separated by purge 'walls' (blue columns). Therefore, self-terminated reactions are achieved by optimizing substrate motion parameters (speed, number of cycles)

3.3. State of the art of Ag reduction in SHJ

SHJ solar cells cannot undergo annealing above 200 °C. To achieve high performance without exceeding this temperature limit, SHJ metallization requires a higher quantity of silver compared to other photovoltaic technologies. Market analysis established the industrial silver consumption at 24.6 mgAg/Wp at the beginning of the project [ITRPV 2022], whereas values below 5 mgAg/Wp are considered an ideal target for the sustainable global production of more than 1 TW of PV per year [Zang 2021].

To reduce silver consumption, the first straightforward approach is to optimize the screen-printing technology used to deposit the metallic grid, through improvements in screen, paste, and grid design. This strategy has already been adopted by several manufacturers since the beginning of the project, and silver consumption values below 17 mgAg/Wp have been demonstrated in photovoltaic research institutes [Lorenz 2023].

A second strategy is to replace silver with other metals such as aluminum or copper. Copper, approximately 1,000 times more abundant than silver, is particularly attractive for SHJ cells. Indeed, as the TCO layer acts as a natural barrier against copper diffusion toward the silicon [Yu 2021], SHJ cells could offer greater robustness against long-term degradation caused by copper diffusion compared to other photovoltaic technologies. Currently, two main strategies are being explored to replace silver with copper in SHJ technology:

1. Screen-printing of copper-based paste

One option to replace silver with copper is to partially substitute the silver content of the paste with copper. This approach allows the industry to maintain the screen-printing metallization technique, which is robust and well-suited to the high-throughput and low-cost requirements of the PV industry.

Currently, most copper-based pastes use copper particles coated with silver to prevent copper oxidation (Ag/Cu pastes) [Zhang 2023]. Since the first proof-of-concept pastes containing 20% to 30% copper in 2022, paste manufacturers have made significant progress in further reducing the silver content. Achieving performance comparable to pure silver pastes and demonstrating the long-term module reliability of this approach are now the main challenges for reaching industrial acceptance.

2. Electroplating of copper

The second strategy, which is a radically different approach to metallization, is based on the electrochemical growth of copper layers (electroplating) [Lennon 2019]. This technology offers the possibility of completely eliminating silver and presents additional advantages. However, it requires additional technological steps to enable the localized growth of copper on the grid. The main advantages of this method are:

- I. Due to copper's high conductivity and the narrow finger width achieved through copper plating, this solution allows for a significant reduction in both finger resistance and shadowing losses, making it a promising method to enhance the electrical performance of solar cells compared to silver screen printing techniques.
- II. The TCO can be made thinner to reduce infrared optical losses while maintaining high electrical properties, such as low sheet resistance. In addition, this thickness reduction directly results in reduced indium consumption, as

introduced in previous Section, making copper-plating a promising solution to reduce both silver and indium consumption at the same time.

- III. Since copper plating does not require curing of the metal, it allows for post-processing annealing to be fully geared toward optimizing the transparent electrodes and passivation films [Geissbühler 2014].

The use of electroplated copper electrodes has been under consideration since the 2010s for homojunction solar cells. The technological and industrial feasibility of this approach has already been widely demonstrated for PERC-type cells. However, for passivated-contact solar cells, such as SHJ, the implementation of copper metallization via electroplating has long been hindered by process complexity [Yu 2021]. Nowadays, several simplified approaches have been developed, such as the one developed by CSEM [Lachowicz 2017], but the technology still faces barriers to market introduction, particularly concerns about module reliability and copper diffusion toward the silicon [Yu 2021].

3.4. State of the art of Si reduction in SHJ

SHJ technology was also selected in the project for its compatibility with thinner wafers compared to other solar cell technologies, which could lead to a significant reduction in silicon consumption and, consequently, a decrease in carbon footprint, as detailed in Deliverable D4.1.

While the standard wafer thickness is progressively being reduced from 160 μm towards 130 μm , recent studies have demonstrated that silicon heterojunction (SHJ) solar cells can maintain excellent performance even on very thin wafers. Efficiencies above 22% have been achieved on wafers as thin as 46 μm [Sai 2019], and more recently, efficiencies of 23.3% with open-circuit voltages (V_{oc}) exceeding 750 mV were reported on 56 μm wafers [Sai 2021]. Similarly, CEA demonstrated V_{oc} values up to 752 mV on 61 μm thick cells processed on a semi-industrial pilot line [Danel 2018]. These results confirm the intrinsic compatibility of the SHJ architecture with ultra-thin wafers, owing to its excellent surface passivation and low-temperature processing. More recently, the potential of thin wafers for high-efficiency devices was further validated by Longi, who reported efficiencies above 25% on 60 μm wafers [Ru 2024].

However, several challenges remain. Mechanically, wafers thinner than 80 μm require adapted automation, handling, and logistics to avoid breakage and defectivity before reaching full industrial manufacturability. Electrically, while wafer thinning improves V_{oc} by increasing the concentration of photogenerated carriers (and also reducing bulk

recombination for cells on low quality or damaged substrates like for spatial applications), it simultaneously limits short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) due to a reduced optical path length (See Figure 3-6). Consequently, even if high efficiencies can be insured down to about $60\mu\text{m}$ today, to achieve very high efficiencies with ultra-thin wafers, the implementation of advanced light-trapping strategies becomes essential [Ru 2024].

Figure 3-6 $I(V)$ parameters of batches of solar cells manufactured on CEA SHJ pilot line for various wafers thicknesses [Danel 2018].

4. Solutions studied in RESILEX

Based on the above literature review, the solutions explored within the RESILEX project to reduce indium and silver content in SHJ solar cells are presented below. These approaches were selected to align with the project's objectives and to support the transition of indium-free and silver-free (or significantly reduced) SHJ solar cells from TRL 5 to TRL 7.

4.1. Reduction or removal of In in SHJ solar cells

1. Reduction of Indium-based TCO thickness: Thin ITO with DARC approach

This was the first approach investigated within the RESILEX project at CEA. The objective was to enhance the maturity and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the thin TCO strategy for indium reduction. To achieve this, large batches of low-indium-content SHJ solar cells were processed on a SHJ pilot line. To reach the indium reduction targeted in the project, the TCO thicknesses were reduced further to what was previously studied at CEA. The ultrathin indium-based TCO layers developed for the front and rear side of the cell were then combined in this project with the addition of a front-side dielectric layer. To facilitate industrial uptake of this innovation, all cell structures were integrated into standard SHJ modules for reliability and aging tests.

2. Replacement of ITO with Indium-Free TCOs: AZO by PVD

CSEM was actively performing In-free TCOs developments by first identifying promising TCOs properties at material level and secondly, by integrating the most promising In-free TCOs into actual solar cells to further study their performance to replace ITO. The In-free TCOs under investigation for the RESILEX project was the aluminum zinc oxide (AZO) which was introduced in previous Sections. AZO is a high resistive In-free TCOs with promising opto-electrical properties to replace ITO in SHJ solar cells. The main challenge in developing AZO is to target low sheet resistance (R_{sh}) as well as high mobility without jeopardizing the optical quality, i.e. while keeping low absorptance. To engineer this TCO with the aim of reaching the best opto-electrical properties trade-off possible, two routes are under investigation for the RESILEX project. First, by adapting the deposition parameters such as the oxygen and hydrogen content inside the deposition gas flow, the deposition pressure, and the temperature. And second, by investigating different PVD targets composition.

In addition, the possibility to increase the TRL of this approach was studied at CEA. Efforts were thus focused on developing AZO deposition processes using an industrial PVD tool integrated into the CEA SHJ pilot line. The resulting AZO layers were evaluated both as standalone TCOs and in combination with a dielectric capping layer on large batches of solar cells processed on a SHJ pilot line. Finally, the reliability of these cells was assessed after integration into standard module configurations.

3. Replacement of ITO with Indium-Free TCOs: Atmospheric pressure SALD-deposited SnO₂

Film optimization for device implementation is a complex process, because both individual and interface properties must be evaluated to assess the role and the performance of a thin film embedded in a multilayer stack such as a SHJ solar cell. In the case of an emerging deposition tool such as AP-SALD, with small size deposition reactor (active deposition area 5 cm²), performance assessment of the developed thin film is feasible only after exhaustive investigation of film properties and limiting features, with consequent identification of optimization axes and strategies. A summary of the research methodology for limiting factors identification and solutions proposal is depicted in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1 Schematics of research methodology for identification of target optimization features of AP-SALD deposited (i)SnO₂ and proposed solutions.

From the target properties to optimize for AP-SALD deposition of TCO, a set of solutions to be investigated by CNRS partner in collaboration with CSEM and CEA are proposed, also depicted in previous Figure (right bottom). The first solution targets to increase carrier concentrations by film doping. The second solution targets investigating passivation of (i)SnO₂ thin films by H₂ post-deposition treatment. The third solution involves modifications in the standard (i)SnO₂ ALD conditions [Nguyen 2022] to target industrial applicability of the developed films, identify properties optimization and address new issues derived from implementation of strategies (1). The detailed methodology for investigating the proposed solutions is schematized in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-2 Schematics of the methodology proposed for studying the different optimization strategies.

4.2. Reduction or removal of Ag in SHJ solar cells

1. Screen-printing of copper-based paste

The first approach investigated at CEA was to reduce silver consumption as much as possible while maintaining the use of the screen-printing deposition technique. Efforts focused on evaluating a wide range of commercially available copper-based conductive pastes on SHJ solar cells, with optimization and testing performed on a pre-industrial pilot line. To meet the project's silver reduction targets, Ag/Cu pastes were applied for the first time to both the rear and front sides of the cells. Initial tests on module integration and reliability were also conducted.

2. Electroplating of copper

To minimize the use of silver in SHJ solar cells, CSEM is developing a copper-plating process that enables the creation of copper metallic grids directly on the solar cells. The copper plating process incorporates two additional steps into the existing SHJ processes which are described in Figure below. First, a thin seed grid is screen-printed onto the front TCO, replacing the conventional silver screen printing. This seed grid could be made of silver (Ag), silver copper (Ag/Cu) or pure copper (Cu) paste. Second, given the conductive nature of TCO, it is imperative to isolate the area between the fingers to prevent parasitic plating, also named ghost plating, on the TCO itself. To achieve this, a full-area dielectric layer, such as aluminium oxide (AlO_x) or silicon nitride (SiN_x), is deposited over the TCO and the seed grid. This dielectric layer serves

as a plating mask and provides an anti-reflective coating (ARC). Finally, copper is electroplated onto the seed grid to form the conductive core of the metal finger. This process is facilitated by the optimization of the dielectric layer's properties, which permit the growth of copper through it, thanks to the voids on the paste particles.

Figure 4-3: Schematics of the process steps that must be added to Figure 3-1 to fabricate commercial bifacial SHJ solar cells with copper electroplating metallization with CSEM process.

Figures below provide more details of the additional process steps required for the copper-plating process of SHJ solar cells as well as microscope images of the seed-grid before and after the copper-plating process.

Figure 4-4 (left) Details of the process steps of copper-plating process performed at CSEM. (right) Microscope images of the screen-printed seed grid and of the copper plated on top of this seed grid.

At CEA, the possibility of printing the seed grid required for copper electroplating using screen-printing techniques with Ag/Cu and pure Cu pastes is explored. The objective

is to print the finest possible lines allowed by the process in order to minimise silver content while ensuring that the printed patterns are suitable for subsequent copper plating. In addition, the feasibility of depositing the dielectric capping layer used in the CSEM electroplating process on an industrial PECVD equipment at CEA was investigated.

4.3. Full process for In-less & Ag-less and In-free & Ag-free SHJ solar cells

To go further, two scenarios, presented in Figure 4-5, for SHJ solar cell fabrication were developed by collaboration between RESILEX project partners. The two scenarios were proposed in Deliverable 4.1 with the aim to combine innovations for the reduction and/or elimination of indium and silver. They were then discussed with WP7 for environmental and economic analysis.

Reference SHJ process	Scenario 1 In-less & Ag-less SHJ	Scenario 2 In-less or In-free & Ag-free SHJ
1) WET chemicals	1) WET chemicals	1) WET chemicals
2) PECVD a-Si	2) PECVD a-Si	2) PECVD a-Si
3) PVD ITO 100 nm Front & Rear	3a) PVD thin ITO 3b) PVD thin ITO + AZO	3a) PVD thin ITO 3b) PVD AZO 3c) SALD AZO
4) Screen-printing Ag paste	4) Screen-printing of Ag-Cu paste	4) Screen-printing of Cu paste
5) Curing	5) Curing	5) Curing
	6) PECVD SiN Front	6) PECVD SiN Front & Rear
		7) Cu plating

Figure 4-5: First version of RESILEX solar cell process scenarios for combining In and Ag reduction, elaborated at the beginning of the project and discussed with WP7.

In Scenario 1, a process was designed to combine indium reduction, achieved through the use of ultrathin In-based TCO layers (with or without AZO) and a front dielectric layer, with the screen-printing of low-Ag-content pastes.

In Scenario 2, the aim was to leverage the dielectric layer used as a DARC to also act as a protective barrier during copper electrodeposition in the CSEM copper metallization process (see Figure 4-6). In this way, the same dielectric layer reduces optical reflection and enables localized copper plating on the seed grid. This approach allows for a fully Ag-free metallization on In-free or In-reduced solar cells, while requiring only two additional steps compared to the reference SHJ solar cell process.

Figure 4-6 Details of the process steps to process the SHJ solar cell of scenario 2.

5. Experiment

5.1. TCO characterizations and main parameters

Characterization of materials prior to their integration in functional solar cells is critical to understand performance improvements or degradation in devices composed of multiple, nanometric scale layers of different nature. In this WP, optical, structural and electrical properties of materials developed (SnO_2 , ITO, AZO) have been controlled using the techniques presented in Table 1. A brief description of these techniques will be done in this Section, to present and clarify concepts to be presented in the results Section.

Table 1 Characterization techniques used for assessing suitability of materials for SHJ device integration.

Optical	Structural	Electronic	Electrical
Spectroscopic ellipsometry			Hall effect
UV-VIS spectroscopy	Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)	Kelvin probe	Four points probe
	Transmission electron spectroscopy (TEM)	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)	IV-characteristics

UV-VIS spectroscopy and spectroscopic ellipsometry are widely used tools to assess optical properties of thin films, using non-destructive methods. UV-VIS spectroscopy allows direct measurement of transmittance, absorbance and reflectance (TRA) spectra by means of monochromated light/sample interaction [Dhruv 2023]. Spectroscopic ellipsometry (SE) provides information on the optical indexes (n,k), TRA spectra; electronic properties such as optical bandgap and optical transitions, optoelectronic properties such as optical mobility and carriers effective masses; structural properties such as thickness, surface roughness and phase composition among other properties [Fujiwara 2018]. In contrast to UV-VIS spectroscopy, SE measures the change in polarization state of a monochromated light beam, therefore this data needs to be converted to the physical properties mentioned above by means of a suitable optical model and optics theory.

For electrical characterization systematic control of the lateral sheet resistance of thin films is done with four points probe. The principle of measurement lies on the application of a small current flow between two points in a line, and measuring the voltage drop between two points contained to the same line, equally spaced. The sheet resistance is calculated as shown in Figure below.

Figure 5-1: Four-points probe setup and calculation of electrical parameters.

Hall effect measurement using Van der Pauw geometry is a modified version of four-points probe, in which a magnetic field perpendicular to the current flow is added, as

shown in Figure below. From the interaction between current and magnetic field, an additional parameter, the Hall voltage (V_{Hall}) can be obtained and the following carrier transport properties can be derived: Carrier density (ND), the number of free carriers contained in the thin film, carrier mobility (μ), the ease of carriers to move throughout the solid network and the carrier type (electrons or holes).

Figure 5-2: Hall effect measurement setup and calculation of electrical parameters.

5.2. Metallization characterizations

Several parameters will be discussed for metallization development. First an example of the metallic grids printed on the cell can be found in the figure below. It contains parallels fingers (horizontal lines) connected by busbar (vertical lines). Depending on the interconnection, the busbar numbers varied on the cells between 0 and 18 in this project. The finger width (w_f) is an important parameter measured by optical microscope it differs from the screen opening from which it is printed due to the viscosity of the paste.

The finger line resistance is the resistance of one centimetre of these fingers and is noted (R_{line}) as seen on the right part of the figure below.

Figure 5-3: (left) Schematic image of the metallic grid with vertical busbar and horizontal fingers (lines) showing the line width (W_f) (right) Schematic image of the cell series resistance showing the line resistance ($R_{S,lines}$) also noted (R_{line}) in this report [Basset 2020].

5.3. Cells characterizations and parameters

To assess the final performance of a solar cell, such as its maximum output power and efficiency, the most fundamental method consists to measuring its current density-voltage (J-V) characteristic under standard test conditions (STCs). STCs are defined by maintaining the cell temperature at 25°C and an irradiance of 100 mW/cm², with a light spectrum that matches the AM1.5g solar spectrum. This spectrum corresponds to an air mass of 1.5, which is the solar spectrum that reaches the Earth when the sun is approximately 41° above the horizon. To characterize the J-V characteristic, the solar cell under investigation is illuminated under STCs, and a sourcemeter is employed to sweep the voltage across a specified range, while measuring the resulting electrical current at each voltage. This process yields a complete light J-V curve of the solar cell, as shown in Figure below. From this J-V curve, the power curve is calculated, and the power at maximum power point (P_{MPP}) of the solar cell is determined. Additionally, other physical parameters are derived from the J-V curve, including the short-circuit current density (J_{SC}), the open circuit voltage (V_{OC}), the fill factor (FF) and the solar cell energy conversion efficiency (eff.). Specifically, the fill factor indicates the squareness of the J-V curve and is calculated as the ratio between the ideal square-shaped curve, defined by the product of the short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) and the open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), and the actual maximum power at the maximum power point (MPP). The efficiency is determined as the ratio of the maximum power output (P_{MPP}) of the solar cell to the power input from the solar spectrum (P_{in}), which is 100 mW/cm². Both parameters are given in equations below:

$$FF = \frac{P_{MPP}}{J_{SC} \cdot V_{OC}}$$

$$eff. = \frac{P_{MPP}}{P_{in}} = \frac{FF \cdot J_{SC} \cdot V_{OC}}{P_{in}}$$

Figure 5-4: Typical illuminated J-V curve of a solar cell together with the related extracted cell parameters.

6. In-less and In-free solar cells

The main objective of this task is to reduce the environmental footprint of silicon solar cells and enhance their sustainability by lowering indium consumption. The amount of indium used in solar cell manufacturing is directly linked to the thickness of the indium-based transparent conductive oxide (TCO) layer. Despite ongoing research efforts to reduce this thickness or eliminate indium entirely, as highlighted in the literature review, current manufacturing processes still rely on approximately 200 nm of indium-based TCO (equivalent thickness on a flat surface).

6.1. Bilayer approach for Indium reduction > 70%

In this section, CEA investigated the possibility of significantly reducing indium consumption by decreasing the thickness of the indium-based TCO layers on both the front and rear sides of the solar cell. Within the RESILEX project, we focused on a bilayer approach for the front side, which involves the addition of a dielectric layer deposited by PECVD (see figure 6-1) with the goal to achieve at least 70% of indium reduction.

Figure 6-1: Schematic SHJ solar cell structure with standard indium consumption (reference) and reduced indium quantity (In-less SHJ).

In order to reach that objective, we developed and tested thinner TCO layers in RESILEX project than those previously studied at CEA and in other research institutes. On the front side, thicknesses ranging from 5 to 15 nm were investigated, while on the rear side, thicknesses of 30 and 40 nm were evaluated.

In addition to the development of thinner layers, efforts were made to improve their conductivity and optical properties. These layers were assessed in large-scale batches

using the SHJ pilot line at CEA. All developments presented below were subsequently integrated into modules for reliability testing. The module-level results are not detailed here and will be reported in Deliverable 4.4.

1. Rear-side TCO reduction at CEA:

Within RESILEX, rear-side TCO layers with thicknesses below 50 nm were tested, enabling progress beyond previous studies conducted at CEA. To enable this reduction, ITO was replaced by a hydrogenated indium metal oxide (IMO:H) with a comparable indium content. The IMO:H layer was first optimized at 40 nm, then further reduced to 30 nm. Results of the 40 nm TCO implementation on the CEA SHJ pilot line are shown in the figure below, and compared with a reference configuration using a 100 nm TCO layer.

A very limited efficiency loss was observed at the cell level, and comparable performance to the reference was achieved at the module level. However, a reduction in the bifaciality factor was noted, attributed to the non-reflective nature of the 40 nm IMO:H rear-side layer. This negative impact will need to be considered when evaluating the overall performance of this approach.

Figure 6-2: IV results of solar cells and mini-modules with rear IMO:H of 100 nm or 40 nm. The bifi coef is the ratio of rear side/front side illumination efficiency measurement [Favre 2022].

2. Front-side TCO reduction at CEA:

On the front side, the DARC (Dielectric Anti-Reflection Coating) approach was investigated within RESILEX to reduce indium consumption by using thinner ITO layers than those commonly reported in the literature. Ultra-thin, highly conductive ITO layers ranging from 5 to 15 nm were developed by tuning sputtering parameters.

The optimized layer properties are summarized in the table below and published in [Gageot 2023]. Results are shown for both with and without the deposition of a SiN_x layer on top of the ITO, and are compared to the standard 100 nm reference. Notably, sheet resistance (R_{sheet}) values below 200 Ω/sq were achieved with 15 nm ITO layers.

Table 2: Electrical properties of the developed ITO layers before and after SiN:H deposition, obtained from Hall Effect measurements. All TCO were deposited on flat c-Si/a-Si:H sub-strates [Gageot 2023]

TCO	Thickness (nm)	R_{sheet} (Ω/sq) before/after SiN:H	Electron concentration (cm^{-3}) before/after SiN:H	Electron mobility ($\text{cm}^2/(\text{V}\cdot\text{s})$) before/after SiN:H
ITO	5	2720 / 969	$1.6 \times 10^{20} / 5.9 \times 10^{20}$	29.2 / 22.0
	10	348 / 286	$5.3 \times 10^{20} / 6.4 \times 10^{20}$	33.9 / 33.9
	15	215 / 185	$6.2 \times 10^{20} / 6.7 \times 10^{20}$	31.2 / 33.5
	100	98	1.40×10^{20}	27.7

The stack combining ultra-thin ITO with a SiN_x capping dielectric was evaluated through optical simulations to optimize module performance. Then, solar cells and modules incorporating these ITO/SiN_x stacks were processed. In this demonstration, three types of electron-selective front-side layers were implemented: one standard amorphous silicon layer (a-Si:H) and two nanocrystalline layers (nc-Si:H and nc-SiO_x:H). The results were published in [Gageot 2023]. In total, 12 experimental conditions were tested, with 8 cells and 3 modules produced per condition. Cell performance results are presented in the table below.

For solar cells with a-Si:H as the front selective layer, IV measurements showed that reducing the front ITO thickness increases the short-circuit current (J_{sc}). However, this improvement is not enough to offset the fill factor (FF) losses caused by the higher sheet resistance of thinner ITO, leading to a drop in overall efficiency. In contrast, using nanocrystalline layers (nc-Si:H or nc-SiO_x:H) reduced the contact resistance in the front-side stack. This lowered the need for lateral conduction in the TCO, which helped limit the negative effects of higher sheet resistance. As a result, these nanocrystalline layers allowed module efficiencies above 22% even with only 5 nm of front ITO, and performances similar to the reference were reached with 10–15 nm layers.

Table 3: IV results (FF, Jsc, Efficiency) after light-soaking (LS) of the cell integration of ultrathin ITOs with a SiN_x/H capping layer. Median values of 8 cells per conditions [Gageot 2023].

Front selective layer	Front ITO thickness	FF (%)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	Efficiency (%)
a-Si:H	100 nm	79.97	38.24	22.50
	15 nm + SiN _x	79.09	38.35	22.30
	10 nm + SiN _x	77.97	38.48	21.97
	5 nm + SiN _x	71.60	38.59	20.28
nc-Si:H	100 nm	81.29	38.37	23.03
	15 nm + SiN _x	80.78	38.31	22.76
	10 nm + SiN _x	80.76	38.36	22.89
	5 nm + SiN _x	78.90	38.53	22.38
nc-SiO _x :H	100 nm	80.61	38.82	23.08
	15 nm + SiN _x	80.46	38.82	22.99
	10 nm + SiN _x	79.72	38.82	22.78
	5 nm + SiN _x	69.22	39.02	19.75

Module aging tests were then performed, and the results will be presented in Deliverable 4.3. These results support the selection of the nc-Si:H selective layer combined with 15 nm of ITO for optimized module performance and reliability.

Additionally, the impact of dielectric composition was evaluated within RESILEX. SiN_x was compared to SiO_x layers as well as to a SiN_x/SiO_x bilayer. The findings, published in [Lanterne 2024], mainly focus on UV stability. In summary, the front-side DARC SiN_x layer demonstrated better UV stability than the alternative SiO_x or SiN_x/SiO_x layers, while also enabling higher overall performance. Consequently, the SiN_x layer was retained for further development in the RESILEX project.

3. Combination of Front and Rear Indium Reduction at CEA:

Within the RESILEX project, we combined for the first time the optimized thin ITO layers on the rear side (30 to 40 nm) with the optimized front-side DARC structure, consisting of 15 nm ITO capped by a SiN_x layer. Both sides feature a significantly reduced indium content compared to previous proof-of-concept devices, resulting in ultra-low indium usage. Specifically, indium reductions of 72.1% and 77.2% were achieved for rear ITO thicknesses of 40 nm and 30 nm, respectively, compared to standard SHJ cells. These cells, illustrated in Figure 6-1, are referred to as “In-less” SHJ within the RESILEX project.

Several batches of 20 to 50 solar cells were processed on the CEA pilot line to implement this combination. Two types of selective layers were tested: nanocrystalline silicon (nc-Si:H) and amorphous silicon (a-Si:H). Solar cell performances were characterized after metal deposition and after a light soaking (LS) treatment, known to

improve the fill factor (FF) of SHJ solar cells. Results were presented at international conferences and published in [Lanterne 2024]. Table 4 below shows median $I(V)$ measurements for each solar cell batch before LS, while Figure 6-3 presents cell parameters before and after LS.

Results before LS (see Table 4), reveal a decrease in FF and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) with reduced TCO thickness, alongside an increase in short-circuit current density (J_{sc}). The FF decrease is attributed to a slight increase in sheet resistance for the 15 nm ITO layer compared to the 100 nm reference, causing reduced lateral conduction. As expected from previous developments, this loss is mitigated when using nc-Si:H. The V_{oc} reduction is explained by increased sputtering damage with thinner TCO layers deposition, that are not sufficiently annealed. Finally, the higher J_{sc} is linked to improved transparency and light management provided by the front-side DARC, combined with a back reflector effect from the thinner rear TCO layer.

Table 4: $I(V)$ parameters measured on each solar cells batch (median values of 20 to 50 cells). All cells with 15 nm of ITO have a SiN_x DARC layer. [Lanterne 2024]

(n) selective layer	ITO (nm)	IMO:H (nm)	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	Eff. (%)
a-Si:H	100	100	737.3	38.08	80.0	22.44
	15	40	736.2	38.19	79.0	22.19
		30	735.2	38.27	78.3	22.04
nc-Si:H	100	100	737.4	38.22	80.1	22.52
	15	40	736.7	38.23	79.6	22.38
		30	736.5	38.26	79.5	22.36

As shown in Figure 6-3, no significant difference in behaviour under light soaking (LS) was observed for cells with thin TCO layers compared to the reference configuration. Following LS treatment, we demonstrated for the first time the successful fabrication of SHJ solar cells on our pilot line with a 77.2% reduction in indium consumption, and a limited efficiency loss of less than 0.08% absolute.

These results must be considered in the context of current industrial benchmarks. The SHJ world-record efficiency, achieved by LONGi, stands at 26.81%. In mass production, SHJ cell efficiencies are known to exceed 25.4% since 2024. Huasun, a key player in SHJ manufacturing, has reported leading mass production efficiencies of 25.5% in 2023 and 26.5% by the end of 2024 [Chunduri 2025].

While direct comparison of pilot-scale and industrial efficiencies requires caution, the very limited efficiency drop demonstrated here of only 0.08%, strongly suggests that a

77.2% indium reduction is compatible with maintaining SHJ mass production efficiencies above 25%.

As next step, these “In-less” SHJ solar cells were subsequently tested in module configuration for reliability and aging analyses. The corresponding results will be presented in Deliverable 4.4.

Figure 6-3: IV results of the solar cells before and after light-soaking (LS) for various indium reduction and two selective layers [Lanterne 2024].

6.2. Replacement of ITO by Indium-free TCO

1. CSEM AZO developments:

As introduced in previous Sections, AZO is a high resistive In-free TCOs with promising opto-electrical properties to replace ITO in SHJ solar cells. The main challenge in developing AZO is to target low sheet resistance (Rsh) as well as high mobility without jeopardizing the optical quality, i.e. while keeping low absorptance. To engineer this TCO with the aim of reaching the best opto-electrical properties trade-off possible, various experiments dedicated to investigating the AZO material properties were performed at CSEM. This deliverable D4.3 presents the main results obtained for AZO developments by optimizing the gas composition used during the PVD deposition. First, the oxygen content was investigated to adapt the PVD target composition. Oxygen is a key parameter to optimize the sheet resistance as well as the transparency of TCOs, such as the higher the oxygen, the higher the transparency but the higher the sheet resistance. Second, hydrogen gas was introduced during the PVD deposition in the gas mixture. Hydrogen is a second key parameter making it possible to decrease the sheet resistance while minimizing the increase of the light absorptance, such as the higher the hydrogen, the lower the sheet resistance but the lower the transparency. By

optimizing these two gases it is possible to find the best opto-electrical trade-off of the AZO.

Figures below show the electrical properties of AZO with variation of oxygen and hydrogen contents, respectively. For oxygen variation, the maximum value of mobility is about $16 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ for the condition with 0 sccm of Ar/O_2 gas flow. This value is still very low compared to the mobility of baseline ITO ($\sim 60 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$). Increasing the Ar/O_2 flow results in a strong decrease of the mobility and a high sheet resistance increase. This mobility decrease and sheet resistance increase can be compensated by a slightly increase of the hydrogen. The increase in hydrogen results in an augmentation of mobility up to approximately $14 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ for 1.5 sccm of Ar/O_2 . This increase is accompanied by a reduction of Rsh, resulting in the lowest value of $\sim 81 \text{ Ohm.sq}$ compared to about 145 Ohm.sq with no hydrogen.

Figure 6-4: Carrier concentration, mobility and sheet resistance as a function of the Ar/O_2 gas flow and a thickness of $\sim 185 \text{ nm}$.

Figure 6-5: Mobility and sheet resistance as a function of the H_2 gas flow for a given Ar/O_2 flow of 1.5 sccm and a thickness of $\sim 185 \text{ nm}$.

2. Developments of interdigitated back contact designs at CSEM for the integration of In-free TCO_2 :

As introduced previously, this WP4 investigates the interdigitated back contact (IBC) architecture as a promising alternative for indium-free SHJ solar cells. This architecture incorporates AZO layer at the back side and is used as a platform for AZO developments and optimizations. Indeed, this architecture remove the constraints of

lateral conductivity inside TCOs, allowing to integrate high sheet resistance TCOs without detrimentally impacting the solar cell performance. In this line, as a first significant development for WP4, CSEM have designed a new IBC SHJ solar cell configuration, consisting of seven 4 cm² solar cells co-processed on a 4" c-Si(n) wafer. This design is depicted in Figures below. This new design with small area SHJ IBC solar cells allows for studying further the potential of optimized AZO once integrated in actual solar cells and to guide our developments. Importantly, the size of 4 cm² is adapted to the SALD deposition system.

Figure 6-6: Seven 4 cm² IBC SHJ solar cells design used for In-Free TCOs developments. (Left) back side and (right) front side.

Figures below show the sheet resistance of AZO layers with or without H₂ as well as LIV parameters of 4cm² SHJ IBC solar cells integrating these AZO layers at the rear. As discussed in previous Section, hydrogen allows for a strong sheet resistance decrease. Looking at the LIV parameters, a slight J_{sc} decrease is observed for AZO with hydrogen which is compensated by FF spreading decrease. Importantly, the V_{oc} are similar for both AZO conditions, demonstrating that the addition of hydrogen doesn't impact the passivation.

Figure 6-7: Sheet resistance of AZO layers with and without hydrogen content.

Figure 6-8: LIV parameters (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF and efficiency) of 4 cm² SHJ solar cells integrating rear AZO layer with and without hydrogen content.

3. CSEM TCO re-hydrogenation:

For the development of indium-free TCOs, post-treatment methods were investigated to further decrease the sheet resistance. The post-treatment methods under investigation include the hydrogenation of TCOs using either a hydrogen-rich atmosphere at a given temperature or by depositing a dielectric capping layer on top of the TCOs, as introduced in previous Section. These methods were investigated in collaboration between CSEM, LMGP, and CEA, and applied to three CSEM baseline TCOs: ITO, AZO, and NSCOT, as well as to the indium-free TCOs deposited by SALD at LMGP.

This section presents the results obtained for the three CSEM TCOs and the next Section presents the results obtained for the LMGP TCOs. To investigate the impact of the hydrogenation, two temperatures of 200 and 400°C were targeted and a silicon nitride (SiNx) was used as capping layers. In addition, both H₂-rich and N₂-rich atmospheres were applied to dissociate the impact of hydrogen and temperature on the TCOs' electrical properties. Figures below show the relative change of the sheet resistance before and after the different post-treatment for the 200°C and 400°C temperatures, respectively. First, the different TCOs present different sheet resistance impact for similar post-treatment. Second, the temperature as, as expected, as strong impact on the sheet resistance decrease, i.e. a higher sheet resistance decrease for the three TCOs and the three condition at 400°C compared to 200°C. In particular, at

200°C, the dielectric as a strong impact on the three TCOs and the H₂-rich atmosphere presents also a strong impact, with a reverse sheet resistance trend observed for the NSCOT. These results demonstrate that these post-treatments are key for the reduction of the sheet resistance. In particular, the dielectric deposition at 200°C is a very promising re-hydrogenation solution compatible with SHJ low temperature process steps. Additionally, as the dielectric layer is a required step of the copper-plating process, this makes it possible to provide both TCOs re-hydrogenation and masking layer at the same time.

Figure 6-9: Relative change of the sheet resistance before and after the different post-treatment: SiNx capping layer, H₂ or N₂-rich atmosphere at 200°C (left) and 400°C (right).

4. CEA AZO developments:

At CEA, our efforts focused on increasing the TRL of this indium-free TCO approach. Two AZO layers were developed using a PVD industrial system integrated into the CEA SHJ pilot line. The two layers, referred to as AZO#1 and AZO#2, differ in the oxygen and hydrogen gas flows used during deposition, resulting in distinct electrical and optical properties. These developments and their corresponding properties were presented at the Silicon PV Conference in 2025 [Gageot 2025].

Table 5: CEA AZO layers characteristics

Material	O ₂	H ₂	comment
AZO#1	+	no	For high FF
AZO#2	++	+	For high J _{sc}

Electrical properties of the AZO layers were assessed by Hall effect measurements for various thicknesses. For AZO#1, thicknesses from 30 nm to 100 nm were investigated, while for AZO#2 50 nm and 100 nm were used. Measurements were performed both with and without a SiN_x capping layer for thin AZO films.

Layers with electrical resistivity comparable to that of ITO were successfully obtained. For 100 nm thickness, the measured sheet resistance (R_{sheet}) was 109 Ω/sq for AZO#1 and 130 Ω/sq for AZO#2, compared to 98 Ω/sq for the 100 nm ITO reference layer. For thinner AZO layers, R_{sheet} increased significantly, reaching up to 570 Ω/sq for 30 nm of AZO#1. The deposition of a SiN_x capping layer slightly reduced the resistance, but R_{sheet} remained too high for solar cell integration below 40nm of AZO. In terms of carrier mobility, the AZO layers showed lower values (10.2 to 12.2 cm²/V·s) compared to ITO (27.7 cm²/V·s).

5. CEA AZO integration in SHJ solar cells:

These AZO layers were evaluated both as standalone TCOs and in combination with a dielectric capping layer on large batches of solar cells processed on the CEA pilot line (see resulting SHJ structures in Figure 6-10).

Figure 6-10: Example of structure of SHJ solar cells with AZO integration on the front side or rear side tested in the project.

AZO was first integrated on the front side of SHJ cells with either a-Si:H or nc-Si:H selective layers. The median parameters of the resulting solar cells are presented in the table below. When replacing ITO with AZO (#1 and #2) while maintaining a 100 nm TCO thickness, a significantly lower current was measured in the AZO-based cells due to the higher absorption of AZO compared to ITO. Despite this drop, AZO#1 exhibited a higher fill factor (FF) than AZO#2.

To overcome the lower optical performance of AZO, thinner AZO#1 layers were tested using a DARC AZO/SiN_x bilayer approach, with AZO thicknesses ranging from 30 to 50

nm. Using this approach, current levels comparable to the ITO reference were achieved when employing nc-Si:H as the selective layer. Moreover, no degradation in surface passivation or fill factor was observed, confirming the suitability of this stack.

This demonstration marks the first successful integration of a “Front In-free” SHJ solar cell on the CEA pilot line, without efficiency loss. This result must be confirmed in larger scale experiment before industrial transfer. However, considering that current industrial references exceed 25.4%, we can conclude on the compatibility of this approach with mass production efficiencies of 25%.

Table 6: IV results (FF, J_{sc}, Efficiency) of the cell integration of ultrathin AZO on the front with a SiN:H capping layer for thin layers. Median values of 8 cells per conditions [Gageot 2023].

Front selective layer	Front TCO	Front TCO thickness	Capping	FF (%)	J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	Efficiency (%)
a-Si:H	ITO	100 nm	no	81.29	38.15	22.88
	AZO#1			80.65	36.49	21.71
	AZO#2			80.00	36.95	21.75
	AZO#1	50 nm	SiN _x	79.17	37.78	22.00
		40 nm		79.74	37.77	22.12
		30 nm		79.37	37.66	21.91
nc-Si:H	ITO	100 nm	no	81.50	37.95	22.81
	AZO#1			80.72	36.58	21.79
	AZO#2			80.30	36.94	21.90
	AZO#1	50 nm	SiN _x	80.55	37.71	22.34
		40 nm		81.38	37.90	22.74
		30 nm		81.36	38.12	22.88

A second demonstration focused on evaluating AZO#1 and AZO#2 as rear-side TCOs in SHJ solar cells, with tested thicknesses of 100 nm and 50 nm. Median performance parameters for each batch are presented in the Table 7.

Both materials show similar behaviour, with FF close to the ITO reference cells and with J_{sc} losses that result in lower efficiency. The current losses, still induced by high absorption, are more limited on the rear side of the cells compared to the front side.

Reducing the AZO thickness from 100 nm to 50 nm slightly improved J_{sc} ($\approx +0.1$ mA/cm²), but had no significant impact on the final efficiency. The best condition identified in this study for a “rear In-free” SHJ solar cell was the use of a 100 nm AZO layer, with a efficiency loss of 0.5% absolute compared to the ITO-based reference.

Table 7: IV results (FF, Jsc, Efficiency) of the cell integration of ultrathin AZO on the rear side. Median values of 8 cells per conditions [Gageot 2023].

Front selective layer	Rear TCO	Rear TCO thickness	Capping	FF (%)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	Efficiency (%)
a-Si:H	IMO:H	100 nm	no	81.29	38.15	22.88
	AZO#1			80.97	37.34	22.38
	AZO#2			80.22	37.33	22.14
	AZO#1	50 nm		80.40	37.44	22.28
	AZO#2	80.67		37.47	22.37	

6.3. Use of non-vacuum techniques for In- free TCO deposition

It has been discussed in the literature review of the previous Section that amorphous SnO₂ deposited at low temperature can be a promising alternative to ITO as In-free transparent contact. Intrinsic SnO₂ ((i)SnO₂) deposited at 200°C reaches resistivity values as low as 10⁻² W.cm at 100 nm thickness, with an average transmittance higher than 75% in SHJ absorption ranges, as shown in Figure 6-11. Nevertheless, lateral conductivities are still lower than state of the art ITO by one order of magnitude. As lateral transport of the transparent electrode is a main factor determining solar cells final efficiency, successful replacement of ITO by (i)SnO₂ films in SHJ solar cells is still limited. In this part, improvements on SnO₂ properties are investigated considering fundamental material properties and process constraints. Compared to industrial scale deposition techniques such as PVD and PECVD, AP-SALD remains an emerging tool.

Figure 6-11: (Left) Transmittance, reflectance and absorbance spectra of 100 nm intrinsic (i)SnO₂ thin film deposited in quartz-glass substrate. (Right) Evolution of the sheet resistance (black) and resistivity (red) of (i)SnO₂ thin films with thickness.

As detailed in Section 4.1, AP-SALD setup was used at LMGP to investigate the properties of SnO₂ deposited in glass and SHJ-like substrates following the three proposed solutions: (1) film doping, (2) film hydrogenation and (3) ALD conditions optimization. Each experiment setup, with their respective constraints will be detailed in the next subsections.

1. Film doping at LMGP:

Intrinsic (non-doped) TCOs are rarely best candidates for solar cell applications, given that state of the art resistivities, in the order of 10⁻⁴ Ohm.cm are difficult to achieve. Recent demonstrations of SnO₂ thin films with resistivities up to 10⁻³ Ohm.cm, deposited by PVD have been reported [Sai 2024] with promising application as TCO in SHJ solar cells. In our case, SALD deposited SnO₂ achieve resistivities up to 10⁻² Ohm.cm. The one order of magnitude difference is mainly attributed to a poor carrier mobility (less than 10 cm²/Vs in our films), and a slightly deficient carrier density (slightly less than 10²⁰/cm³). Carrier density can be fixed by tuning of O₂ content in the thin film or by film passivation, which will be explored in next sections. In contrast, carrier mobility (μ) is mostly dependent on the availability of s-atomic orbitals provided by the metallic cation (Sn in our case) rather than the oxygen anion [McLeod 2012]. Therefore, increased μ can be achieved either by increasing the Sn- content in the thin film (and thus decreasing the interatomic distance between Sn cations), or by addition of a second metallic cation as a dopant. The latter solution was explored in this part.

In this work, we have investigated two ways of incorporating a second cation on the base TCO film: Co-dosing and supercycle [Macco 2022]. Each of the strategies consider a different SALD setup. In the case of film doping, the first challenge addresses the incorporation of a second metal cation to the SALD process of SnO₂, keeping the ALD deposition conditions of the latter. To this aim, we have assessed two doping strategies: co-dosing and supercycle. Co-dosing refers to a process in which the two cations are injected to the reactor through a shared line, whereas in supercycle an additional line carries the second metal precursor to a separate region in the reaction space. The main advantage of co-dosing is the ease of technical implementation, while the main challenge is the control on the doping fraction, especially when the metal precursors present very different reactivity. In contrast, the supercycle approach requires a more sophisticated setup, which remains the main challenge for achieving good deposition control and reproducibility.

The first and most important barrier for the controlled integration of a second cation in the SALD reactor was linked to technical limitations of our laboratory setup in LMGP. Therefore, important modifications in this line were made (details will not be given in

this report due to confidentiality constraints). Nevertheless, successful demonstration of the controlled deposition of a bi-cation layer was achieved. Results are currently under publication and will not be detailed in this report. Additionally, the novel SALD setup is currently under optimization and no significant improvements on SnO₂ doping for photovoltaic applications have been achieved up to date.

2. Film hydrogenation at LMGP:

In metal oxide semiconductors, carrier mobility can be impacted by the network arrangement (crystalline, amorphous, etc), by the atomic orbitals involved in conduction, atomic radii of the cation, passivation, among others. Electron conduction in low mobility semiconductors can be compensated to some extent by higher carrier densities, keeping in mind that very high carrier densities ($>10^{22}/\text{cm}^{-3}$) can further hinder electronic transport and transmittance. In our case, (i)SnO₂ mean carrier density is in the order of $10^{19}/\text{cm}^3$. Carrier mobility less than $10 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ results in lateral conductivities varying from 2 to 40 S/cm. The challenge is thus to find strategies for depositing higher μ , Nd films with better reproducibility, without sacrificing T%.

Hydrogen has been widely used as passivating agent in solar cells, given its ability to suppress dangling bonds, which has been also reported as beneficial for transparent electrodes [Seron 2022][Park 2024]. In the case of SnO₂, it has been reported that Hydrogen incorporation by plasma treatments within a temperature range between 200°-600°C causes reduction to metallic Sn at the surface and thus considerable losses in T% [Minami 1989][Major 1986]. Therefore, we have explored the effect of thermal annealing under Ar-H₂ and N₂ atmosphere, in order to avoid high-energy treatments that could deteriorate film properties. The main objective is to try to decorrelate the impact of hydrogen incorporation and temperature on the surface of SnO₂ samples and identify potentially beneficial effects to improve transport properties of the film.

In this experiment, we investigate the effect of hydrogen incorporation in as deposited intrinsic SnO₂ thin films by thermal annealing at 200° and 400°C, using an IR oven at CEA and a FGA-RTP (forming gas anneal – rapid thermal process) tool at CSEM. All samples were deposited and characterized in quartz-glass substrates. The main objective is to measure the impact of annealing in SnO₂ electronic transport properties, interface properties and optical properties. For this aim, we have characterized the as-deposited film properties before and after annealing with four-points probe, Hall effect measurements, Kelvin probe, UV-VIS transmittance, and spectroscopic ellipsometry. We have also performed annealing under N₂ atmosphere in control samples, to separate the thermal annealing effect from the H₂ incorporation on the film. Results shown in this report correspond to experiences realized at CEA with the IR-thermal annealing furnace. During the experiments, samples were annealed under N₂ or Ar/H₂

mixture for 35 minutes. Due to technical constraints, Ar-H₂ mixture was injected for 60 seconds in 4 minutes intervals, as shown in Figure below.

Figure 6-12: Schematics of annealing time and gas mixtures used for hydrogenation of SnO₂.

Electronic transport properties, measured with Hall effect are depicted in Figure below. It can be noted that after annealing under N₂ atmosphere the sheet resistance is the most affected parameter under annealing at 400°C, with values increasing an average of 3.4 times after annealing. The same trend is observed for annealing under Ar-H₂, but R_{sheet} values are increased up to 20 times, with the consequent decrease in conductivity. Additionally, carrier mobility and carrier density are also strongly impacted in the latter case, being divided by three and ten after annealing at 400°C. In contrast, under annealing at 200°C, Nd increases an average of 1.7 times, with a small impact in carrier mobility and R_{sheet}, thus compensating the loss in conductivity. The nature of additional carrier density after Ar-H₂ annealing is unclear and must be further investigated, but it is possible that defect passivation occurs within the SnO₂ layer after H₂ annealing.

Figure 6-13: Electronic transport properties (carrier density N_D , carrier mobility μ , sheet resistance R_{sheet} and conductivity σ) of SnO_2 samples measured before (red) and after (blue) annealing under N_2 and Ar-H_2 atmospheres at 200 and 400°C.

To have deeper insights, we have measured the UV-VIS-NIR transmittance of the annealed samples and calculated the bandgap energies using the Tauc approach. Results, depicted in Figure below (a) show that annealing at 400°C results in a bandgap decrease from 3.52 to 3.36 eV while after annealing at 200°C no significant variations in the bandgap are observed. Bandgap variations can be due to structural modifications of the semiconductor lattice or the introduction of electrically active impurities. In addition, IR transmittance spectra, shown in Figure below (b) in the range 1500-2500 nm show that under Ar-H_2 annealing at 400°C optical transmittance is significantly increased, while after annealing at 200°C it remains unchanged. A similar trend is observed under N_2 annealing, but less pronounced as the loss of Nd is less significant (not shown in this report). Therefore, it is likely that H_2 in SnO_2 acts as a passivating agent.

Figure 6-14: (a) Tauc-plot of SnO_2 transmittance spectra between 3.0 and 4.0 eV. Energy bandgaps are calculated from the x-axis intersection of the linear part of the curve (between 3.7–4.0 eV); (b) Complete transmittance spectra (280–2500 nm) of SnO_2 as deposited (red line) and annealed under Ar-H_2 atmosphere (blue lines) at 200 and 400°C.

These experiments are being completed with thermal annealing using the FGA-RTP tool at CSEM, a morphological and electronic characterization of the as deposited and treated surfaces, and deposition and treatment on SHJ-like test structures. More insights on the passivating effect and the best conditions of hydrogen incorporation will be investigated.

3. ALD conditions optimization for SHJ applications at LMGP

The third proposed solution concerns experimental investigations on the ALD conditions allowing conformal and controlled film deposition, and at the same time providing industrially interesting deposition rates. While the SnO_2 film deposited with AP-SALD by [Nguyen 2022] shows promising properties for photovoltaic applications, demonstrated film growth rates are found around 0.08 nm/ALD-cycle following previous ALD developments [Nazarov 2015]. In an effort to improve deposition rates to more attractive ranges, we have explored the management of O_2 in the AP-SALD reactor, enhancing the contribution of the base oxygen co-reactant to SnO_2 film formation, H_2O . We have studied the impact of these modifications in film transport properties, transmittance spectra and surface morphology.

Results are currently under exploitation and will not be detailed in this report, however, we have found favourable conditions for increasing growth rates of about 1.5 times with respect to the reference procedure.

Conclusions and outlook

In this Section, strategies for optimization of SnO₂ deposited with AP-SALD and tested in SHJ solar cell-like structures have been discussed. Three main optimization targets have been identified on this In-free proposed as a replacement of ITO transparent electrode in SHJ solar cells: (1) doping of the intrinsic SnO₂ film to increase carrier mobility, (2) performing post-deposition hydrogen-based treatments to explore potential improvements in electrical transport properties and (3) modifying ALD deposition conditions in order to increase deposition rates towards more industrially compatible processes. Preliminary conclusions, proposed further actions and limitations for further work are listed in the Table below

Optimization target	Preliminary conclusions	Further actions	Limitations
(1) Doping	AP-SALD doping setup designed and demonstrated.	Test optimal conditions to deposit doped SnO ₂ thin films.	Technical skills for machine setup optimization.
(2) Hydrogenation	Annealing at 200°C under Ar-H ₂ atmosphere results in passivation of SnO ₂ films.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding the role of H₂ in SnO₂ passivation. - Comparison to hydrogenation of other TCOs studied in this WP in collaboration with INES and CSEM. - To find optimal hydrogenation conditions. 	Application of the potential benefits of passivation in SHJ devices can be constrained by the success of optimization target (1).
(3) ALD conditions	Addition of O ₂ in the N ₂ barrier channels of AP-SALD reactor contributes to increase deposition rates by a factor of two	-Electrical and electronic characterization of SnO ₂ deposited on SHJ test structures	-

7. Ag-less and Ag-free solar cell

This section presents the main results of WP4 developments on Ag-less and Ag-free SHJ solar cells. For a better understanding of the results, it is worth recalling that the market analysis established the industrial silver consumption at 24.6 mgAg/Wp at the beginning of the project [ITRPV 2022], whereas values below 5 mgAg/Wp are considered an ideal target [Zang 2021]. During the project, a significant reduction in silver consumption was reported in the industry, with current values ranging from 14 to 18 mgAg/Wp [Chunduri 2023].

7.1. Screen-printing approach for Ag reduction > 70%

The first approach investigated at CEA was to reduce silver consumption as much as possible while maintaining the use of the screen-printing deposition technique.

1. Screen-printing design optimization at CEA:

In the initial phase of the RESILEX project, CEA concentrated its efforts on optimizing the screen-printing process to reduce silver usage. This was achieved through process adaptations such as modifying the screen angle and refining the metallization design. These optimizations led to a reduction in silver line thickness, enabling the fabrication of SHJ solar cells with 19.2 mgAg/Wp, corresponding to a 22% reduction in silver consumption compared to the project's baseline. This was achieved on a 6-busbar (BB6) configuration, with no significant impact on performance (an efficiency loss of <0.1% absolute was recorded) [Favre 2022]. At the time, this result represented the state of the art, and it remains consistent with the most recent industrial advances.

2. Use of Ag/Cu pastes for screen-printing at CEA:

Following the initial optimizations, CEA focused on evaluating silver-coated copper (Ag/Cu) pastes as an alternative to pure silver pastes for screen-printing metallization. These pastes, composed of copper core particles coated with silver, offer a promising route toward further silver reduction while maintaining electrical performance.

To demonstrate this approach and raise its Technology Readiness Level (TRL), a wide range of commercially available Ag/Cu conductive pastes was screened throughout the project on CEA's pre-industrial pilot line. The screen-printing process was

continuously optimized for these new materials, in parallel with an ongoing benchmarking effort as new pastes became available on the market.

For this study, SHJ solar cell precursors were fabricated on M2-size wafers, featuring a 100 nm ITO front TCO and a 100 nm hydrogenated indium metal oxide (IMO:H) rear TCO. A 6 Busbar metallization pattern was screen-printed on both sides of the wafers. After the curing step, the cells were electrically characterized via I(V) and line resistance (R_{Line}) measurements. Ag/Cu pastes from various suppliers were tested and compared against a reference pure silver paste. These pastes were applied either on the rear side only (with pure Ag paste on the front side) or on both the front and rear sides of the cells (Front & Rear configuration). For each configuration (see figure 7-1), a minimum of 25 solar cells per batch was processed to ensure statistical relevance.

Figure 7-1: Ag consumption per watt-peak of the solar cell in correlation of the median efficiency loss for the rear only and the Front&Rear integration of the Ag/Cu pastes (CEA results before M12).

The results are presented in Figure 7-2 (batches processed before M12) and Figure 7-3 (batches from M12 to M30). These figures show the measured silver consumption in mgAg/Wp for each paste, correlated with the efficiency loss compared to the pure silver reference.

Rear side Ag/Cu:

Overall, the results underline that the use of Ag/Cu pastes on the rear side can have almost no impact on the solar cell efficiency with adapted pastes. It was confirmed by simulation that the line resistance increase with Ag/Cu pastes has no impact on the FF when implemented on the rear side. With Ag/Cu paste on the rear, Ag consumption as low as 15.9 mgAg/W was first obtained with an efficiency loss below 0.05%. Further work has conducted a further decrease of this value down to 13.8 mgAg/W without efficiency loss (<0.05%).

Figure 7-2: Ag consumption per watt-peak of the solar cell in correlation of the median efficiency loss for the rear only and the Front&Rear integration of the Ag/Cu pastes (CEA results before M12).

Figure 7-3 Ag consumption per watt-peak of the solar cell in correlation of the median efficiency loss for the rear only and the Front&Rear integration of the Ag/Cu pastes (CEA results at M24 and M30). [Lanterne2 2024].

Front & Rear side Ag/Cu:

In order to reach the targeted value of Ag consumption, the use of Ag/Cu paste on the front and rear sides seems necessary. However, when applied on both sides of the cells, higher FF losses are measured due to the larger impact of the line resistance on the front.

Thanks to improvements in paste formulation and tighter control of screen-printing processes, the latest results from the CEA pilot line demonstrated the feasibility of achieving a total silver consumption as low as 10.9 mgAg/W, while maintaining an efficiency loss limited to 0.04%. When compared to the industrial reference of 24.6

mgAg/W at the beginning of the project, this result represents a 55% reduction in silver usage, without compromising performance. The negligible efficiency loss further supports the compatibility of the Ag/Cu metallization approach with 25% efficiency SHJ cells in mass production, where average efficiencies already exceed 25.4%.

Other Ag/Cu pastes tested, showed potential for even further reductions in silver content. A minimum silver consumption of 6.8 mgAg/W was achieved in one batch, corresponding to a 72% reduction compared to the baseline. However, this condition also led to an efficiency drop of 0.42%, which is considered too high for industrial viability. These results highlight that for pastes with high electrical resistivity, alternative metallization designs, such as increasing the number of busbars or transitioning to a busbarless architecture, may be necessary to mitigate performance losses.

Next step:

To support the industrial implementation of these developments and advance the technology readiness level (TRL), further investigations were carried out on the impact of the substitution of Ag paste by Ag/Cu paste on module interconnection, long-term reliability, and certification over a 30-year lifetime. The outcomes of these analyses will be detailed in Deliverable 4.4.

7.2. Cu plating solution for Ag-free solar cells

To develop and optimize the copper plating (Cu-plating) process, several cross-experiments were performed between CSEM and CEA. The different cross-experiments focus on the investigation of (i) the curing and drying processes applied on the seed-grid printed by CEA, (ii) further optimization and investigation of Ag/Cu pastes developed by CEA for the seed-grid as well as (iii) the integration of pure copper seed-grid printed at CEA and their compatibility with the Cu-plating process of CSEM, (iv) the investigation and optimization of dielectric layers deposited at CEA and CSEM and their ability to promote the Cu-plating process and finally, (v) continuous improvement of the Cu-plating process. This deliverable presents the main results of these Cu-plating cross-developments performed for the RESILEX project which are grouped in three topics: a) metallic seed-grid developments, b) dielectric optimization and c) Cu-plating optimization for thick and thin ITO.

a) Metallic seed-grid developments

In order to develop copper-plated metallization without silver for the solar cell, a copper-based seed grid must be printed before the copper plating step. As a first important step, the screen-print design to print the metallic seed grid was discussed and optimized to meet the requirements for nine busbars soldering and plating pads at CEA, as well as to fit with the system used to perform the Cu-plating process at CSEM.

At CEA, the challenge was to print the thinnest lines possible in order to reduce the silver quantity and the overall line width after plating, thereby limiting optical losses, without causing line interruptions. Ag/Cu pastes from four suppliers (P1 to P4) were selected and tested for this application. The pastes were printed using screens designed with very small finger openings of 20 μm and 17 μm .

Results presented in Figure 7-4 show that P1 and P3 are not suitable for fine-line printing. For both pastes the line widths remains above 30 μm even with a 17 μm opening and both pastes present strong spreading areas as observed in Figure 7-5. As the spreading areas will be covered by copper during plating this will consistently increase the shadows area on the cells. However, P2 and P4 appear suitable for fine-line printing, as the tests result in finger widths around or below 30 μm for the 17 μm opening. This corresponds to a paste laydown reduction of 60% compared to standard screen openings and thus significantly reduces the Ag consumption compared to the screen-printing approach described in Part 7.1. For some pastes, a strong increase in line resistance is measured with the 17 μm opening, highlighting the presence of finger interruptions.

Figure 7-4 (left) finger line width and (right) finger line resistance measured for the four Ag/Cu pastes, for finger openings of 20 μm and 17 μm [Lanterne2 2024]

Figure 7-5 Finger width images of the four Ag/Cu pastes printed with a screen opening 17 µm [Lanterne2 2024].

Following these results, P2 and P4 were used for cross-experiment with CSEM.

Figures 7-6 depicts the width and height of the Ag/Cu seed-grid (with P2 paste) and of the final fingers after Cu-plating process. In this demonstration, the SCCP seed-grid (Ag/Cu P2) was successfully printed with fingers featuring thin width of about 30 µm and a height between 9.6-10.5 µm. After the Cu-plating, a significant widening of the seed-grid fingers is observed, but the final width is close to 45 µm widths, which corresponds to the actual width of the baseline silver print. The height of the final fingers stands between 12.7-18.0 µm. Thus, the process is compatible with solar cell fabrication as it does not increase the shadow area of the metallic grid as compared to standard screen-printed metallization.

Figure 7-6 Microscope images of the SCCP seed-grid and of the final fingers after Cu-plating process as well as value of their respective width and height.

To characterize further the metallization, the line resistance of the grid was measured before and after the Cu-plating process and data are plotted in Figure 7-7. These results demonstrate that the CSEM Cu-plating process was successful on the CEA SCCP seed-grid (P2). A final line resistance lower than 0.7 Ohm/cm is reached, even starting from very high values after SCCP (up to higher than 10 Ohm/cm). These results demonstrate that the seed-grid line resistance is not a limiting factor, thus removing

constraint on the Ag/Cu paste properties. This opens the way to investigate further full copper paste (featuring higher line resistance) and to target thinner finger width.

Figure 7-7 Average values of the line resistance of the front and rear metallization measured before and after the Cu-plating process, and for both ITO thickness of 30 and 100 nm.

Further developments of the screen-printed Ag/Cu seed-grid were then performed at CEA resulting in optimized print of P4 paste. The best results of the project were obtained with this Ag/Cu paste and are presented in Figure 7-8. The Figure highlights that the seed-grid features very good geometrical properties, with a smaller line width between 19.3 and 27 μm and a line height in the range of 4.3 to 7.9 μm . The copper plating applied on top of this seed-grid (P4) after a dielectric deposition demonstrate very good coverage of the seed grid as well as good geometry of the final fingers presenting state of the art line width for SHJ with values between 37.3 and 39.2 μm .

Figure 7-8 Confocal microscopy images of (a) the Ag/CU seed grid screen-printed at CEA with paste P4 and (b) the final copper plated finger from the Cu-plating process performed at CSEM [Lanterne3 2024].

b) Dielectric optimization

To optimize the Cu-plating process various dielectrics were investigated. The dielectric must be optimized to be able to promote Cu-plating on the seed-grid location (through the dielectric itself) as well as to provide electrical isolation to avoid any unwanted plating on the TCO. Indeed, as the TCO is a conductive material, it is imperative to isolate the area between the seed-grid fingers to prevent parasitic plating on the TCO. As the main outcomes of these developments, the table below presents the results of the Cu-plating quality for two different ITO thicknesses, 30 nm and 100 nm (i.e., two different ITO conductivities), as well as for three dielectrics: two different aluminum-oxide (AlO_x) layers with a thickness of 8 nm deposited at CEA, and the CSEM baseline dielectric. These developments demonstrated that, on one hand, the two different 8 nm thick AlO_x layers from CEA have physical properties, such as low porosity, which unfortunately inhibit the Cu-plating process. Consequently, these layers were found to be unsuitable for Cu-plating. On the other hand, both conditions with 100 nm and 30 nm thick ITO, combined with the CSEM dielectric, presented high-quality Cu-plated grids. This indicates that the ITO thickness does not impact the Cu-plating process and final finger quality.

Table 8 Summary of the different conditions with the ITO thickness (100 or 30 nm), the dielectric layers as well as the status of the Cu-plating.

Condition	ITO	Masking layer	Cu-plating quality
1	100 nm	CSEM dielectric	Ok
2	30 nm	CSEM dielectric	Ok
3	100 nm	CEA AlO _x -1 8 nm	Inhibited
4	100 nm	CEA AlO _x -2 8 nm	Inhibited

Based on these results, the CSEM dielectric masking layer has been further optimized to achieve better uniformity in the copper electrodeposition on the seed grid. For this development, the seed grid was screen-printed at CEA using silver copper coated paste (SCCP). A comparison of the initial copper electrodeposition using a standard dielectric layer (silicon nitride SiN_x) deposited on an industrial PECVD tool and the CSEM optimized dielectric layer is shown in Figure 7-9 below. Comparing both conditions, it is observed that the CSEM optimized dielectric layer enables proper and complete coverage of the entire seed grid with high homogeneity, while the SiN_x layer shows silver spots, resulting in lower homogeneity and thus lower copper-plating quality. This demonstrates that the CSEM optimized dielectric masking layer provides

high-quality copper-plating fingers and establishes the CSEM optimized dielectric as a robust baseline for the Cu-plating process at CSEM.

Figure 7-9: Top row: initial copper deposition in dependence of the dielectric layer; Bottom row: after deposition of several microns copper; Test on precursors with silver-coated-copper (Ag/Cu) paste P4 provided by CEA.

c) Cu-plating optimization for thick and thin ITO

After the development of the dielectric layers, investigations were conducted with the aim of studying the performance of Cu-plating process on thin ITO compared to reference 100 nm thick ITO. For these investigations, two major development approaches were undertaken.

CEA thin ITO:

For these investigations, SHJ M2 solar cells with two different ITO thicknesses were processed at CEA. The first group of solar cells featured 100 nm thick ITO layers on both the front and back sides, while the second group of solar cells featured 30 nm thick ITO layers on both sides. Both groups are completed by the CSEM-dielectric deposited on both sides. The light IV (LIV) curves were measured at CSEM before and after copper plating to investigate the final solar performance as well as the quality of the Cu-plating process, and the results are presented in Table below. For the LIV measurement, the interconnection is performed using a thermally controlled gold chuck as well as nine pogo-bars to connect the nine busbars present on the solar cells (see Figure below).

Figure 7-10: Interconnection of the nine busbars (BB) using nine pogo-bars on a thermally controlled gold chuck for the light IV curves measurement at CSEM.

First for group 1, a gain in FF is observed thanks to the strong reduction of the line resistance after Cu-plating. Conversely, a decrease in J_{sc} is observed, likely due to the widening of the metallic grid and/or suboptimal anti-reflective coatings (ARC) of the dielectric layers on the 100 nm thick ITO. For group 2, the FF is not improved by the Cu-plating process, which could be due to the non-optimized rear side 30 nm thick ITO, highlighting the importance of improving the electric properties of this TCO. In contrast here, a J_{sc} gain is observed thanks this time to the dielectric layer providing a more optimal ARC by completing the thin 30 nm ITO layer. Finally, for both groups the V_{oc} is demonstrated to not be impacted by the Cu-plating process. Overall, these results are very promising and demonstrate further the potential of performing Cu-plating on the 30 nm ITO, i.e. on In-less solar cells.

Table 9 Average values of the LIV parameters of the solar cells from group 1 and 2, before (SCCP) and after (Cu) Cu-plating process.

Group	Process	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (mV)	FF (%)	Eff (%)
Group 1: CSEM-dielectric & 100 nm ITO	SCCP	37.7	734.9	78.7	21.8
	Cu	37.1	733.3	79.7	21.7
Group 2: CSEM-dielectric & 30 nm ITO	SCCP	34.8	730.6	77.4	19.7
	Cu	36.7	730.7	77.4	20.7

CSEM Cu-plating process developments on different seed-grids and thinner ITO:

For these developments, CSEM investigated the copper plating on industrial precursor SHJ solar cells with 50 nm ITO on both sides and using either silver-paste (SP), silver

copper coated-paste (SCCP) and a paste containing only copper particles (Cu) which were screen printed at CSEM. Figures below show the line dimensions obtained before and after plating process as well as EDX maps of cross sections of plated lines for the three pastes under investigation.

Figure 7-11 Line dimensions before and after plating. As printed: width 27-30 μm , height 8-13 μm . After plating: width 33-34 μm , height 14.5-17.5 μm

Figure 7-12 EDX maps of cross sections of plated lines, a) copper plated on Ag paste, b) copper plated on Ag paste with only copper signal, showing copper electrodeposited also within paste particles, c) copper plated on silver-coated-copper paste, and d) copper electrodeposited on pure copper paste.

First, the 50 nm ITO using the SCCP paste was studied and compared to the reference ITO using full silver-paste. Both pastes were screen printed on SHJ solar cells. LIV results obtained are shown in Figures below. Remarkably, same efficiency as reference has been achieved with reduced ITO thickness and with silver-coated-copper paste containing 50% silver. The gain in current is mainly due to the anti-reflecting coating provided by the CSEM dielectric and the gain in FF is due to the improvement of the finger's conductivity after copper-plating. These last results are

illustrated in the next Figure presenting the line resistance before and after the copper plating. For the three metallic pastes under study, the copper plating provides a strong resistivity decrease resulting in a strong series resistance reduction in SHJ solar cells. Finally, the copper plating is still demonstrated to not impact the passivation of the SHJ solar cells, demonstrating stable or even slightly higher V_{oc} .

Figure 7-13: LIV data before and after process with dielectric layer and electrodeposited copper.

Second, the 50 nm ITO using the pure copper paste was studied and compared to the reference using full ITO silver-paste. In this case, the copper paste has been applied only on the back side of the cell because only wide lines ($>50 \mu\text{m}$) could be obtained. Figure below shows the high resistivity of the copper seed-grid after screen-printing resulting in a line resistance which is initially two orders of magnitude higher than that of silver or silver-coated-copper paste. However, after plating, highly conductive lines are obtained and the improvement in efficiency is accordingly very high (+15% relative) [Paviet-Salomon 2024].

Figure 7-14 On the left: line resistance busbar-to-busbar on cells as received (SP) and after the plating process (+Cu) on front (F) and back (B). On the right: efficiency of group E with pure copper paste on the back, before and after plating.

8. Results toward ultimate scenarios

In order to go further to what was previously presented we assessed in the RESILEX project the simultaneous reduction of In and Ag. This section presents the main results of the WP4 developments, which combine optimized solutions for In-less/In-free as well as Ag-less/Ag-free SHJ solar cells.

The processes tested in this report are summarized in the figure below. It should be noted that the In-free cells with AZO were tested in Scenario 1 instead of Scenario 2. Additionally, we decided to focus the CSEM tests using copper plating metallization (Scenario 2) on the more advanced “In-less” SHJ cells with thin ITO precursors processed at CEA, as these have demonstrated reliability at both the cell and module levels within the project.

Reference SHJ Process	Scenario 1 In-less or In-free & Ag-less SHJ	Scenario 2 In-less & Agless or Ag-free SHJ
1) WET chemicals	1) WET chemicals	1) WET chemicals
2) PECVD a-Si	2) PECVD a-Si	2) PECVD a-Si
3) PVD ITO 100 nm Front & Rear	3a) PVD thin ITO 3b) PVD thin ITO + AZO 3c) PVD AZO	3) PVD thin ITO
4) Screen-printing Ag paste	4) Screen-printing of Ag- Cu paste	4a) Ag-Cu seed-grid 4b) Cu seed-grid
5) Curing	5) Curing	5) Curing
	6) PECVD SiN Front	6) PECVD SiN Front&Rear
		7) Cu plating

Figure 8-1: Two alternative scenarios for SHJ processes investigated in the WP4 of RESILEX.

8.1. CEA Results toward scenario 1

In-less and Ag-less SHJ at CEA:

In this part we combined our development for Ag/Cu metallization with low-indium containing SHJ precursors. Two main indium reduction strategies were implemented: the use of ultra-thin ITO layers (72% of indium reduction) and a combination of thin ITO with AZO layers (80% of indium reduction) as presented in Figure 8-2.

Figure 8-2 : SHJ solar cells structures of reference process and of scenario 1 process with Ag/Cu metallization for 3a (thin ITO) and 3b (thin ITO + AZO) options.

For this demonstration SHJ solar cells were process on M2 size n-type CZ wafer on CEA pre-industrial line. We used a standard metallization pattern of 6 busbars. For

each condition, large batches of 25 to 50 cells were processed. Several versions of the rear IMO:H of 40 nm were tested. Electrical performances of 4 batches of these cells are presented on table 10 for the best IMO:H version. I(V) measurements were performed after a Light-Soaking step.

Table 10: IV results (Isc, Voc, FF, Efficiency) after light-soaking (LS) of various condition of “In-less” SHJ with Ag or Ag/Cu metallization. Median values of 25-50 cells per conditions.

Batch	PVD Front	PVD Rear	paste	I(V) Median Post LS			
				Isc (A)	Voc (V)	FF (%)	Eff (%)
B1	ITO 100 nm	IMO:H 100 nm	Ag	9.44	0.735	81.7	23.19
B2	ITO 15 nm	IMO:H 40 nm	Ag	9.44	0.733	81.6	23.11
B3	ITO 15 nm	IMO:H 40 nm	Ag/Cu	9.43	0.733	80.8	22.89
B4	AZO 30 nm	IMO:H 40 nm	Ag/Cu	9.41	0.733	78.1	21.97

First, we could confirm our previous results on “In-less” SHJ with the results of Batch 2. Indeed, we demonstrate once again a very limited absolute efficiency loss of 0.08% for the configuration with a 72% indium reduction compared to reference cells, with a consistent number of processed cells. This result is achieved thanks to the optimized front and rear thin-TCO layers and the integration of a SiN_x dielectric capping layer on the front side.

In parallel, the results of Batch 3 show the impact of implementing Ag/Cu metallization on these “In-less” cells. In this experiment, the Ag/Cu metallization corresponds to a 62% reduction in silver consumption compared to standard Ag metallization, calculated from the Ag content in the paste and the weight of paste laydown. A fill factor (FF) loss can be observed when using Ag/Cu metallization on “In-less” SHJ cells, mainly attributed to increased line resistance on the front side. However, with this batch, we demonstrate an industrial process for SHJ solar cells with a 72% indium reduction and a 62% silver reduction, leading to a median absolute efficiency loss of only 0.3%. This loss remains within a tolerable range for industrial application, as it should not affect the ability to produce SHJ cells with efficiencies above 25%, while reducing solar cell costs, as it will be discussed in WP7. Moreover, there is room for improvement by adapting and optimizing the front-side metallic grid design for this structure and reduce this loss.

Finally, the use of very thin AZO layers (30 nm) on the front side, combined with a SiN_x capping layer, was tested with Ag/Cu metallization (Batch 4 in Table 10). This process enables further indium reduction but results in a more significant increase in resistive losses (FF loss), leading to an absolute efficiency decrease of up to 1.2%.

These results demonstrate the technical feasibility of significantly reducing both indium and silver consumption in SHJ cell manufacturing, with limited efficiency losses compatible with current industrial standards. Solar cells implementing In and Ag reductions were then integrated in module for long term reliability testing.

In-free and Ag-less solar cells at CEA:

In this part we combined our development for Ag/Cu metallization with indium-free SHJ precursors thanks to the implementation of developed AZO layers on the front and rear side. On the front side the AZO 30 nm combined with a SiN_x layer was selected for its best performances. Several metallization conditions were tested on these “In-free” precursors: a Ag metallization, a Ag/Cu metallization on the rear or a Ag/Cu metallization on both sides.

Figure 8-3: SHJ solar cells structures of reference process and of scenario 1 process with the 3c option (In-free cells with full AZO) and with Ag/Cu metallization applied on the rear side only or on both sides of the cells.

For this demonstration SHJ solar cells were processed on high quality M2 size n-type CZ wafer on CEA pre-industrial line. We used a metallization pattern of 6 busbars. For each condition, large batches of 25 to 50 cells were processed. Several Ag/Cu pastes were tested. Electrical performances of the 6 batches of these cells are presented on table 11 and Figure 8-4. This experiment was a joint experiment at CEA with the European project NEXUS. The NEXUS project aims at combining the cells structures presented in Figure 8-3 with a Perovskite solar cell to form a Tandem (PK/Si) device. With this experiment NEXUS will assess the In and Ag reduction impact on Tandem solar cells.

Concerning the results on simple junction solar cells (see table below) we can note a significant impact on the current in this “In-free” approach and a loss in the FF. Both parameters explain the efficiency loss of 1.2% between reference SHJ and “In-free SHJ” of Batch 2.

Table 11: IV results (I_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF, Efficiency) after light-soaking (LS) of various condition of “In-free” SHJ with Ag or Ag/Cu metallizations. Median values of 25-50 cells per conditions.

Batch	PVD FAV	PVD FAR	pâte FAV	pâte FAR	I(V) Median Post LS			
					I_{sc} (A)	V_{oc} (V)	FF (%)	Eff (%)
B1	ITO 100 nm	NSCOT 100 nm	Ag	Ag	9.31	0.745	82.3	23.38
B2	AZO 30 nm	AZO 100 nm	Ag	Ag	9.07	0.742	80.3	22.15
B3	AZO 30 nm	AZO 100 nm	Ag/Cu 1	Ag	9.00	0.740	79.3	21.59
B4	AZO 30 nm	AZO 100 nm	Ag/Cu 2	Ag	9.00	0.741	79.5	21.72
B5	AZO 30 nm	AZO 100 nm	Ag/Cu 1	Ag/Cu 1	9.07	0.742	80.0	22.01
B6	AZO 30 nm	AZO 100 nm	Ag/Cu 2	Ag/Cu 2	9.04	0.734	79.5	21.61

The implantation of Ag/Cu metallization as a low impact on the efficiency as compared to the indium removal. A limited additional 0.2% of efficiency loss is measured in the best case for copper-based metallization integration. With this experiment the demonstration of In-free SHJ with Ag reduction of 61% was done at CEA with a median efficiency loss of 1.4%

Figure 8-4: Efficiency measurement of the cells for each batch before and after light soaking (LS).

8.2. CEA & CSEM cross-experiment results toward scenario 2

To develop high efficiency indium and silver-less SHJ solar cells additional cross-experiments between CEA and CSEM were performed. These cross-experiments aim at developing the Cu-plating approach of CSEM on the optimized “low-Indium” SHJ solar cells (>70% of Indium reduction) developed at CEA. These SHJ solar cells feature

40 nm of IMO:H at the back side and 15 nm of ITO on the front side as well as Ag/Cu seed-grid on both sides (See Figure 8-4). The Ag/Cu implemented was previously optimized and investigated at CEA (P2 or P4 from part 7.2). These cells are then completed by dielectric deposition at CEA or CSEM before the CSEM copper-plating process on both sides (see Figure below). The grid pattern is made for a 9BB interconnection, and the solar cell are processed on n-type Cz wafer featuring a M2 size.

Figure 8-5 Schematic (left) CEA reference SHJ solar cells with thick TCO and silver grid as well as (right) of optimized indium-less and silver-less solar cells (scenario 2) processed with thin TCOs, additional dielectric layers and Cu-plating process [Lanterne 2 2024].

Best results of copper-plating on “In-less SHJ:

The best results of the integration of copper plating on “In-less SHJ” was obtained in the third cross-experiment between CEA and CSEM. The seed-grid was deposited by screen-printing at CEA using P4 Ag/Cu paste. The optimized dielectric and plating steps were then processed at CSEM.

Solar cells performances were compared to the reference process of this batch (Ag screen-printed metallization with standard In-based TCO (see structure in Figure 8-5). The results are shown in the figure 8-6 below. In this experiment we measured the performance at each process steps of the copper-plated cells. Figure 8-7 shows the solar cell efficiency after LIV measurements for the reference cell as well as for the Cu-plated solar cells after (i) screen printing of the seed-grid, (ii) after the CSEM dielectric depositions and (iii) after the Cu-plating process with the final copper fingers.

In this experiment we can first notice a reduced V_{oc} on “In-less + copper plating” SHJ due to the TCO thickness reduction without using nc-Si:H selective layers. This impacts the overall efficiency of our cells.

On Figure 8-7 we can observe a strong efficiency gain of about 1.6%_{abs} after dielectric deposition. This owes to a significant increase in both J_{sc} and V_{oc} induced by the properties of the dielectric layer which, on one side, complete the anti-reflecting thickness of the thin ITO and on the other side, improve the passivation quality. A

second efficiency gain of about 0.16%_{abs} is observed after copper plating. This is explained by a strong FF increase due to significant line resistance decrease induced by the growth of the copper plated fingers on top of the thin Ag/Cu seed-grid. Overall, the final efficiency after copper-plating, i.e. of SHJ solar cells with 72 % of Indium reduction and significant reduction of Ag, presents high values up to 22.05% and only 0.23% of absolute efficiency loss as compared to the reference at 22.28%. Moreover, this loss can be easily reduced by the implantation of nc-Si:H selective layer.

Figure 8-6 LIV parameters J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF and efficiency of SHJ solar cells of reference solar cells and In-less with Cu plating metallization solar cells [Lanterne3 2024].

Figure 8-7 Efficiency of the reference SHJ solar cells as well as of the optimized low-indium Cu-plated SHJ solar cells after the screen-printed seed-grid, after dielectric deposition and after the Cu-plating process [Lanterne3 2024].

These results demonstrate that the copper-plating process performed at CSEM as a strong potential for the “low-Indium” SHJ solar cells (>70% of Indium reduction)

developed at CEA and is a very promising solution to target significant indium and silver reduction in SHJ solar cells. Even if 25% of solar cells efficiency was not demonstrated here due to the performances of reference solar cells, the very limited loss of 0.23% validate a compatibility of the process with 25% of efficiency in industry where baseline (reference) SHJ have reached 26.5% in 2024 [Chunduri 2025].

Importantly, the question arises whether such thin ITO layers are suitable to provide sufficient long-term protection against humidity and copper. To assess stability, mini-modules integrating copper-plated cells with thin ITO were fabricated at CSEM using the OBB interconnection. These mini-modules are currently being tested at CSEM and have demonstrated stable performance after 500 hours of damp-heat aging, with no change in Voc. The tests are still ongoing and will be discussed in deliverable D4.4.

Process compatibility with industrial PECVD:

Second, dielectric investigations were conducted at CSEM and CEA. The optimized CSEM dielectric was compared to a silicon nitride (SiN_x) deposited at CEA with an industrial PECVD tube. I(V) characterizations were performed to investigate the solar cell performance and the quality of the Cu-plating for both dielectric layers under investigation. Figure 8-8 shows the I(V) parameters (J_{sc}, V_{oc}, FF and efficiency) after copper-plating process for the two dielectric layers.

Figure 8-8 LIV parameters J_{sc}, V_{oc}, FF and efficiency of SHJ solar cells with final Cu-plating for two different dielectric layers which are the optimized CSEM dielectric as well as the CEA SiN_x deposited by industrial PECVD tube furnace [Lanterne3 2024].

Thanks to the copper plating step optimization for both dielectric as presented in part 7.2b a continuous copper plating was obtained for case A and B (see previous Figure 7-9). The lower homogeneity of the copper plating on the industrial SiN_x dielectric results in a lower FF. However, both dielectric results in high efficiency solar cells with

similar values close to 22%. Significantly, these results demonstrated that the copper-plating process is compatible with industrial SiN_x deposition in PECVD tube.

Test of Ag-free SHJ:

To further develop the seed grid with the aim of completely removing the silver, a novel Cu paste consisting of micron-sized particles has been investigated at CEA for the seed-grid deposition and completed by the copper-plating process at CSEM. Preliminary results show that the paste is strongly oxidized after curing in air at CEA thus resulting in a highly resistive line. The very high line resistance of the seed grid conducts to a partial copper deposition under standard plating process conditions (See Figure 8-9b. This negative effect was minimized using a modified pre-treatment, demonstrating that copper coverage could be improved Figure 8-9c. However, the initial solar cell efficiency of 5% abs after seed-grid screen-printing was only slightly higher, reaching 10% abs. Presumably, the curing conditions were not optimal, leading to excessively high line and contact resistance. Based on these results, ongoing developments are being conducted to improve the electrical properties of this pure-copper seed grid at CEA.

Figure 8-9: Pure Cu paste seed-grid printed on 15 nm ITO, a) after curing in air, b) with dielectric layer and plated at standard conditions, c) after plating with modified conditions.

9. Silicon reduction

As discussed in part 3 of this report, the potential to process high-efficiency SHJ solar cells using thin wafers has already been demonstrated, paving the way for a significant reduction in silicon consumption. In the RESILEX project, we investigated the impact of indium reduction by processing "In-less" SHJ solar cells on thin silicon wafers.

For this study, several batches of busbarless SHJ solar cells were fabricated on M2 (244.3 cm²) wafers in the CEA pilot line using two processes: the Reference process, as described in Figure 8-1, and the "In-less" SHJ process developed in Section 6.1. The "In-less" process corresponds to a 72% reduction in indium compared to the reference, with 15 nm of ITO on the front side and 40 nm of IMO:H on the rear. After screen-printing and curing, an additional PECVD step was used to deposit a dielectric layer, forming a DARC structure.

Both processes were applied to silicon wafers of two different thicknesses, corresponding to 165 μm and 65 μm , respectively. The I(V) parameters of the cells are shown in Figure 9-1. The usual V_{oc} improvement observed for thinner wafers is confirmed for "In-less" SHJ. In fact, a higher increase was even measured in that case, with an average V_{oc} gain of 12.5 mV. Thanks to the DARC approach, higher current was measured for "In-less" SHJ as compared to the Reference SHJ. The expected current (I_{sc}) drop for thinner wafers was observed in both processes. However, "In-less" SHJ on 65 μm wafers still exhibited higher current than the reference cells on 65 μm wafers.

In the end, the efficiency loss when reducing wafer thickness to 65 μm is more pronounced for the "In-less" SHJ (a loss of 4.8%abs, compared to 3.1%abs for the reference) due to larger FF losses. As shown in Figure 9-1, the FF values for "In-less" SHJ on 65 μm wafers display significant dispersion in this batch, highlighting potential issues related to the manufacturing of 65 μm wafers such as breakages, that could be related to the addition of a PECVD step.

Figure 9-1: $I(V)$ parameters of SHJ solar cells process on CEA pilot line for 4 conditions, Reference or In-less processes on 165 μm or 65 μm wafers.

10. Conclusions

The report highlights the consequent efforts and works produce in the WP4 of RESILEX for the development of sustainable and eco-designed heterojunction solar cells. State of the art results and demonstrators have been produced in each approach investigated in the project. The reliability analysis of the fabricated solar cells through aging tests has been a continuous work in parallel of these developments all along the project, guiding the selection of the best developments. The reliability results will be presented in the next deliverable D4.4.

Concerning the project objectives:

- We have demonstrated in this report an industrially compatible process for manufacturing passivated contact solar cells (SHJ) which is In-free (thanks to Aluminium zinc oxide deposited by PVD) and with a copper-based metallization (by screen-printing of copper-based paste). The results show an overall efficiency loss of 1.4% absolute for this process.
- In addition, SHJ solar cells featuring a 72% reduction in indium content and integrated a copper-based metallization were processed using two different approaches for the metallization (screen-printing of copper-based paste and copper plating). Both approaches have shown high-performance results with negligible performance losses compared to the reference batch, thus being compatible with solar cell efficiencies of 25%.

Detailed conclusions for each approach developed to reduce In or Ag can be found below:

- The reduction of the In-based TCO layer thickness, for In reduction above 70%
For the first time, the possibility to reduce indium content in SHJ solar cells by 77.2% while decreasing the cell efficiency by less than 0.1% absolute was demonstrated. State-of-the art developed ultra-thin ITO of 15 nm was used on the front side for this demonstration, with an additional SiN_x anti-reflective layer, combined with a reduced and optimized IMO:H (indium metal oxide) layer of only 30 nm on the rear side. The performance losses were minimized thanks to the use of nc-Si:H selective layers. The robustness of the approach was confirmed several times on a pre-industrial line. The processing of several large-scale batches has enabled us to raise the TRL of the approach to level 7, while using a particularly low in content as compared to other research. Finally, the process was also proven to be compatible with silver and silicon

reductions, as detailed in the report. Next on-going step, with already promising results, is the assessment at module level of the “In-less” SHJ solar cells.

- The development of AZO layers as In-free TCO by PVD

Concerning the developments of indium free TCOs by PVD, we demonstrated aluminum zinc oxide (AZO) layers with interesting electrical properties. Thanks to an optimized hydrogen dilution in the deposition gas flow, it was possible to increase the mobility and decrease the sheet resistance for a fixed value of oxygen content and a given AZO target. In addition, we engineered small area SHJ IBC design to conduct advanced indium-free TCO developments. This architecture reduces the impact of lateral transport on solar cell performance, allowing us to focus our studies on passivation and optical performance resulting from the integration of indium-free TCOs. The SHJ IBC structure is thus a promising alternative for In-free SHJ solar cells. Moreover, post-process TCOs re-hydrogenations were conducted to investigate the possibility of further reducing the sheet resistance. These investigations demonstrated that dielectric layers are a very promising re-hydrogenation solution compatible with SHJ low-temperature process steps. Significantly, as the dielectric layer is a required step in the copper-plating process, we demonstrated that the deposition of a dielectric layer can provide both TCOs re-hydrogenation and a masking layer simultaneously.

Additionally, the AZO layer deposition was developed on pre-industrial PVD equipment and integrated into a pilot-line process for standard SHJ. Layers with promising performance were obtained and implemented on the front side and/or rear side of SHJ cells. In this way, we successfully demonstrated the integration of a “Front In-free” SHJ solar cell on the CEA pilot line, without efficiency loss, as well as a fully “In-free” SHJ cell with an efficiency loss of only 1.2%. As with the previous approach, the stability of these cells under humidity is of particular importance. Aging tests and module reliability results will be presented in the next report.

- The development of SnO₂ films as In-free TCO using an atmospheric pressure, low temperature and low environmental footprint spatial atomic layer deposition technique (AP-SALD):

Regarding the development of In-free TCO by means of AP-SALD, we have investigated the applicability of SnO₂ thin films as transparent electrode in SHJ solar cells. We have demonstrated that low electron mobility is the main limiting factor resulting in lateral sheet resistances, about one order of magnitude higher than state of the art ITO films. We have proposed and explored ways for improving the electrical properties of SnO₂ through doping, hydrogenation and tuning of chemical composition. We have developed

a SALD doping module that allow us to deposit mixed cation films with precise control in thickness and composition, and currently we are working on applying this setup on the fabrication of doped SnO₂ thin films. Hydrogenation of SnO₂ thin films (ongoing experiment) points out to a passivating effect of H₂ on the thin films, that can potentially help in increasing electron densities without an effect in mobility. Additionally, we have worked on the optimization of the deposition process to achieve deposition rates that are more compatible with industrial processes.

Further work will be focused on optimising the doping (supercycle) SALD technique, on comparing the effect of H₂ of different SnO₂ recipes with other TCOs studied in this project, and on characterizing different SnO₂ recipes in SHJ device.

- The use of copper containing paste deposited by screen-printing

Regarding the use of copper-containing paste deposited by screen-printing, results have demonstrated the robustness of the process with large batches of solar cells processed on a pre-industrial line. A continuous improvement in silver reduction and performance was achieved during the project, thanks to industry efforts in developing new Ag/Cu paste formulations. By using these new pastes and applying tighter control over the screen-printing process, the latest results obtained on the pre-industrial line demonstrated the feasibility of achieving a total silver consumption as low as 10.9 mgAg/W, while maintaining an efficiency loss limited to 0.04%. Compared to the industrial reference of 24.6 mgAg/W at the beginning of the project, this result represents a 55% reduction in silver usage without compromising performance. The best results conducted to silver consumption as low as 6.8 mgAg/W in the RESILEX project (corresponding to a 72% Ag reduction). These results are ahead of current industrial practices and in line with achievements from other institutes.

- The use of copper electroplating process

Regarding the development of copper-plating process, we demonstrated that this process is a very promising solution to significantly reduce both indium and silver consumption in SHJ solar cells at the same time. Copper-plated SHJ solar cells with strong indium reduction (>70%) demonstrated efficiencies close to the references during our different investigations. In addition, this work allowed for significant optimization of the copper-plating process at different levels with a demonstration of (i) optimized Ag/Cu seed-grid and preliminary results of full copper seed-grid, (ii) optimized dielectric masking layers allowing for avoiding gosht plating, improved anti-reflecting coating, TCOs re-hydrogenation and optimal copper fingers growth, as well as (iii) optimized copper-plating process with technological solutions close to industrial processes. In conclusion the project significantly contributed to further optimize and develop the copper-plating process, with the aim of transferring this technology to industry.

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**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.